

DAUNTLESS BRAVERY: UNVEILING THE EXPERIENCES OF FEMALE SINGLE PARENT TEACHERS

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Dauntless Bravery: Unveiling the Experiences of Female Single Parent Teachers

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Abstract

This study aimed to describe the experiences of the female teachers who are single parents by focusing on the description of their significant experiences, their coping mechanisms, and the insights that they can share. The researcher employed a qualitative-phenomenological approach as the research design. The participants of the study were the ten teachers for the in-depth interview and ten teachers for the focus group discussions. These teachers are from the Municipality of Alabel, Province of Sarangani. The findings indicated that in the experiences of the teachers, four (4) emergent themes emerged, and these are: patiently taking responsibilities, good in managing time, experiencing financial instability, and becoming optimistic. On the other hand, in terms of the coping mechanism of the teachers, six (6) major themes emerged when the data was analyzed: overwhelming support from significant others, enriching one's spirituality, loving oneself, acceptance of the reality, possessing stronger personality, and focusing on the responsibilities. Lastly, in terms of the insights that the female single parents could share based on their experiences, six (6) major themes emerged: resiliency, feeling the pain until it hurts no more, never forget to pray, face life positively, managing finances well and be an inspiration. These could become the basis in crafting specific programs and projects which would benefit the female teachers who are single parents.

Keywords: *educational management, single parenting, female teachers, phenomenology, philippines*

Introduction

"Just because I am a single mother does not mean I cannot be a success."

- Yvonne Kaloki

The quote explains that being a single mother does not hinder anyone from being a successful person. Despite their situation, single mothers could also become successful in their work and lives. These mothers have attitudes of being fearless or dauntless and brave. Dauntless bravery means being courageous to combat every life battle. It is the best metaphor for female single parents, who may have their battles in life but can still succeed in any endeavor. The author emphasized that single mothers can do everything they want and succeed. In the United States, people categorize single parents as individuals who are divorced from their partners and raise their children on their own alone. In addition, they are responsible for running the home and assisting with the child's growth (Nishioka et al., 2021).

On a global scale, especially in Pakistan, parenting is the foundation and support of the enormous institution that is the family. Parents are responsible for educating their children about social standards, values, and emotional and psychological development. Single parenthood is not widely accepted in our society. Single parents and their children are stigmatized by society. Because of patriarchy, unmarried moms are highly stigmatized in Pakistan in particular. Living with parents who are the opposite gender is not accepted in most cultures. A parent significantly impacts a child's health, personality, and conduct. In our situation, a girl cannot readily discuss every minor concern with her father as she may with her mother, and the opposite is true (Gading, 2019).

The researcher also has friends and colleagues who are female single parents. The researcher was astonished by how they overcame their daily struggles for their children. It inspired and motivated her to conduct this study. Also, the researcher has not come across any study in the Province of Sarangani focusing on the experiences of the teachers, who are single mothers. This study was conducted since there is a need to help these teachers as they encounter problems with their lives as solo parents. It motivated the researcher to conduct this study basing on the many friends she has who are single mothers, and most of them are teachers.

Numerous studies have already been conducted on the experiences of single mothers or solo parents. However, the respondents in the study were students and other non-professionals. Only limited studies focused on the lives of teachers who were considered single parents or single mothers. This research wanted to address the gap as it would also unveil the teachers' experiences. This study was conducted to shed light on the challenges female single parents encounter as they navigate single parenthood while also playing their roles as teachers.

Research Questions

This study sought answers to the following research questions:

1. How do the female single parent-teachers describe their experiences?
 - 1.1. how do the female single parent-teachers view themselves as female single parents?
 - 1.2. how do the female single parent-teachers cope with their challenges?
 - 1.3. what are the insights of the female single parents about their experiences?

Methodology

This section covers the research technique, research design used in this study, philosophical presumptions, the researcher's function, research informants, the selection procedure, data collecting, data analysis, reliability, and ethical issues to be adhered to.

Research Design

This study used the qualitative phenomenological research method to describe the experiences of female single parents, focusing on their views of themselves, their feelings towards being single parents, and how it affects their teaching performance. This study took a qualitative approach, used phenomenology in tradition, used hermeneutics in discipline, and interpreted it in an interpretative manner.

This study used a qualitative technique to help the researcher understand the lived experiences of female single-parent teachers to respond to the research questions. The research questions assume that people interpret their experiences and attribute understanding to their lived experiences. Qualitative studies provide insights into human behavior, emotion, and personality traits that quantitative studies cannot.

Authentic reporting, first-hand experience, and quotes from honest conversations are all used in qualitative research to try and gain deeper insight. It seeks to comprehend how the participants interpret their environment and how that interpretation affects their actions. Furthermore, a qualitative "approach" is typically a method of approaching subjective research. It explains the goals, the role of the researcher or researchers, the phases of the study, and the data analysis technique, either directly or implicitly (Hennink et al., 2020; Silverman, 2020; Trochim, 2020).

In contrast, qualitative research is a beneficial inquiry approach for thoroughly digging and studying to understand and learn about a central phenomenon. The researcher will pose broad, generic inquiries to the informants or participants to get the participants' comprehensive opinions in words or images. The information acquired will then be analyzed for themes and descriptions. It depends on the reality constructed by individuals, where multiple realities exist that must be faithfully reported based on the voices and interpretations of the informants. It employs an inductive approach. It is a value-laden investigation that is influenced by the situation in which the researcher is working (Creswell et al., 2019; Kuscuoglu & Hartas, 2022; Walther et al., 2017).

Furthermore, qualitative research is a subset of social science research that involves collecting and analyzing non-numerical data to provide insights into social life by examining particular groups or places. It is the observation and interpretation of people's perceptions of various events and captures people's perceptions in a natural setting (Gentles et al., 2017).

Furthermore, qualitative researchers were interested in people's beliefs, experiences, and meaning systems as seen through their eyes. Statistical analysis and empirical calculations are not part of qualitative research. Qualitative research has its roots in social and cultural anthropology, philosophy, psychology, history, and sociology. The qualitative tradition seeks a "deep understanding of the specific problem." Qualitative research aims to generate new concepts and theories by systematically describing and interpreting issues or phenomena from the perspective of the individual or population being studied. The questions determine the chosen methodology (Viswambharan & Priya, 2018).

A phenomenological inquiry is also used to learn about how we think and feel in the most direct ways. It emphasizes what happens within the person to reach and describes lived experiences. This method was chosen because it is a discipline that focuses on people's perceptions of the world in which they live and what it means to them, a focus on people's lived experiences (Sundler et al., 2019). Furthermore, it enables the researcher to delve into the perceptions, perspectives, understandings, and feelings of those who have witnessed or lived through the phenomenon or situation of interest.

A phenomenological study also has seven main features. These characteristics include deciding on a phenomenon to investigate, identifying a group of individuals who have experienced it, discussing the theoretical framework guiding the phenomenological study, an explanation by the researcher regarding their personal experiences (known as bracketing), a data collection procedure commonly involving interviewing individuals who have experienced, and data analysis procedures that move from narrower significant s to broader significance (Qutoshi, 2018).

Furthermore, hermeneutic phenomenology aims to produce rich textual descriptions of selected phenomena in the lives of individuals who can connect with the experience collectively. It focuses on individuals' and groups' subjective experiences. Furthermore, it attempts to reveal the world as the subject's experiences through their life-world stories (Kafle, 2018; Standing, 2017).

Finally, the study is phenomenology in tradition, hermeneutics in discipline, and thematic in interpretation. Hermeneutical phenomenology is a procedure that causes educational agents to reflect on their personal experiences and professional work to improve. It analyzes the essential aspects of this experience, giving them the necessary sense and importance. The "phenomenology favors the understanding of the school realities, emphasizing the experience of the educational process representatives" (Dangal & Joshi, 2020; Dibley et al., 2020).

Hermeneutic phenomenology is concerned with the lived life world or human experience. The emphasis is on illuminating details and seemingly insignificant aspects of experience that we may take for granted daily to create meaning and achieve a sense of

understanding. Husserl and Heidegger disagreed on how to proceed with this exploration of lived experience. While Husserl was interested in acts of attending, perceiving, recalling, and thinking about the world, Heidegger was interested in 'Dasein,' literally meaning 'being in the World.' Husserl saw humans essentially as knowers, and he was concerned with actions of attending, seeing, recalling, and thinking about the environment (Nigar, 2020; Oerther, 2020).

Participants

As mentioned in the previous parts, twenty (20) single-parent female teachers from the Municipality of Alabel participated in this study. An inclusion criterion was set. These teachers are widowed and legally separated from their husbands. They have already taught for over five (5) years as permanent teachers in the Department of Education, Sarangani Division.

Data Collection

The method I used to collect data was consistent with the study's research focus. As a result, the researcher conducted in-depth interviews to gather information. In-depth interviews are standard techniques in the design of narrative inquiries. It enables critical informants to use their own words, allowing the researcher to examine the perspectives and develop insights into how key informants interpret their reality of the phenomenon under consideration. The protocols to be followed in the study, which will be observed before, during, and after the interview, are of primary consideration in data collection (Moser & Korstjens, 2018).

The first step in data collection is to obtain permission and schedule an interview. To begin with, the researcher sought permission to conduct research from the Ethics Research Committee (ERC) to ensure the ethical conduct of the research. The researcher also secured the approval of the Dean of the Graduate School. Upon approval, the researcher obtained permission from the Dean and the Schools Division Superintendent of Sarangani, Sir Gildo G. Mosqueda, CEO VI, the Public Schools District Supervisor in Alabel District, the School Principals of the identified participants, and the research informants. The conduct of in-depth interviews is the second stage of data collection. To build rapport with the key informants, all interviews began with a brief orientation on the research title and intended outcomes. Privacy and confidentiality in data handling were discussed, as well as the documentation protocols. During the interview, the researcher requested permission to take photographs, record the proceedings on video or with a similar device, take notes during the interview, make transcriptions, and code for analysis. The researcher created a friendly atmosphere to make the interviewee feel at ease. This welcoming environment helped participants overcome their initial doubts and fears. The need to triangulate the data is a way to ensure consistency of answers, which builds the credibility of the data gathered; as a result, a focus group discussion was held in which key informants could participate. The key is to plan activities so that they do not interfere with one another.

Finally, the final stage in data collection was retrieving all data records, including notes, pictures, and recordings. A brief review of notes was conducted to create an inventory of all collected data. Following the completion of transcriptions from recorded media, key informants were contacted to clarify and confirm their unclear answers. The researcher was responsible for the data's security, care, and confidentiality.

Data Analysis

The analysis process entails making sense of the words or texts and images comprising the study's data. The audio and video of the taped interview were converted into textual data in this step. Thematic analysis was used to interpret the meanings of the textual data. In this study, the researcher interpreted the data using Thematic Analysis. Thematic analysis is the most relevant for any study that attempts to discover through interpretations. It adds a systemic dimension to the analysis of the results. It allows the researcher to compare the frequency of a theme with one of the contents. It adds precision and complexity to the analysis and improves its overall sense. Various dimensions and data must be understood and collected for qualitative analysis. (Clarke & Braun, 2017).

Additionally, it is the most widely used type of data analysis. This method employs a six-step approach, the first of which is becoming acquainted with the data by reading and re-reading it. The second step is to code or label the entire text to be easily grouped and analyzed. The third step is to create themes from the labeled data that address the problem statement. Commonalities and patterns are combined to form a coherent concept about the phenomenon under investigation. The fourth step is to review the themes corresponding to the entire data set and the problem statement. The fifth step is to define the theme and name it. The sixth step is to put everything on paper by creating a write-up that includes interview narratives. Thus, in interpreting data, this study will use Thematic Analysis (Clarke & Braun, 2017).

This study followed the six phases of Clark & Braun's framework for conducting a thematic analysis: Step 1: familiarize themselves with the data; Step 2: create preliminary codes; Step 3: search for themes; Step 4: review themes; Step 5: define themes; and Step 6: write-up.

Ethical Considerations

There are apparent ethical implications for this qualitative investigation. The methodology employed in this study may be primarily to blame for these issues and concerns. The pertinent ethical concerns in this field of research were maintaining proper study operation, confidentiality, and anonymity. The researcher had personally approached each participant and extended the invitation to participate. Protocols such as written and verbal consent were also observed; permission was sought through a letter addressed to each participant.

This study followed the standards of the RMMC Ethics and Review Committee for the guidelines of ethical consideration, particularly in addressing the population and data such as, but not limited to:

Voluntary Participation. Participants were allowed to participate without expecting consequences, compensation, or loss of benefits. Therefore, the participant's rights to contribute to the body of knowledge were carefully considered and anticipated when the study's goal and its advantages were explained to the participant. The subjects in this study were not coerced into taking part. When individuals were participating in the study and began to feel uncomfortable, they were allowed to end their involvement.

Privacy and Confidentiality. Participants' privacy rights shall not be violated without their informed agreement following the Data Privacy Act of 2012, which safeguards this fundamental human right. Allowing respondents to omit their names from the consent form is one technique to maintain privacy and confidentiality in this quantitative study. Additionally, secrecy and privacy were achieved by withholding the informants' demographic information, such as age, gender, occupation, employment, and disease. Therefore, for safety reasons, their identity was kept a secret. Even their answers to the survey questionnaire questions were kept private and taken into consideration.

Informed Consent Process. As completely as possible within the study's parameters, prospective research participants were thoroughly informed of the study's objectives, procedures, and advantages. The fact that the respondents' consent was obtained demonstrates that their involvement was voluntarily requested. It was done in writing, outlining all the vital information that needed to be shared with the participants and how the survey was carried out. The informed consent form required the participants to sign it, indicating they voluntarily agreed to participate in the survey. There was no need for parental consent because the participants were willing adults. The names of the respondents did not appear in the survey questionnaire, and their answers were kept confidential. The participants knew they could withdraw from participating in the study at any time.

Recruitment. The reasons why the respondents had agreed to participate in the study were explained to them so that the respondents could comprehend the purpose of the study. The researcher discussed the study's goal and main points with them so that they could understand them more clearly. In addition to the letter, the researcher explained the purpose and importance of the study.

Risks. Only if the benefit-risk ratio is acceptable and favorable research has been done. In this study, keeping the participants safe from severe damage was equally crucial. The participants' welfare was given priority in the study. They were also not harmed because their identities were kept secret. Their safety and security were first and foremost. It was important for the researcher to confirm that the participants were emotionally, physically, and socially prepared. The researcher ensured they did not feel uncomfortable or unpleasant when responding to the questions.

Benefits. The findings of this study were helpful to the teachers because they had the eyes of the DepEd officials, school administrators, and female teachers who were single parents. Additionally, for the study to be beneficial, the researcher followed all precautions that would not endanger the participants' lives and would be advantageous for future endeavors involving linked studies. The most essential thing for all to achieve benefits is the rise of meaningful learning. Additionally, this might contribute to achieving Sustainable Development Goal #4, ensuring students get a high-quality education.

Plagiarism. There was no hint or proof that the research had misinterpreted someone else's work. The study was checked for plagiarism using programs such as Grammarly or Turnitin. A researcher must possess moral virtues and values, such as good character and honesty. The researcher must know more about plagiarism to produce a respectable research report.

Fabrication. The study did not show or hint that what had been done had been intentionally misinterpreted. There was no deliberate drawing of incorrect inferences or fabrication of data or results. The researcher used and integrated the hypotheses relating to the data and other inferential notions.

Falsification. There was no evidence in the study of overclaim or exaggeration, nor was there any indication that the work had been purposely misrepresented to meet a model or theoretical expectation. Additionally, this study did not adhere to data manipulation, which entailed coming up with generalizations or omitting crucial information, as well as modifying materials, tools, or procedures to deceive others.

Conflict of Interest (COI). The study lacked any indication of a conflict of interest (COI), which is a set of circumstances where a professional's judgment about a primary interest, like the welfare of participants or the validity of the research, tends to be influenced by a secondary interest, like financial or academic gains or recognitions. Furthermore, the researcher, who had no authority or influence over the respondents, forced them to participate in the survey.

Deceit. There was no proof that the study deceived the participants about any possible risks. Study participants' rights must be strictly upheld, mainly if they have finished postsecondary education; hence, appropriate and reasonable norms must be observed.

Permission from Organization/Location. The study's researcher adhered to procedures. After receiving the go-ahead from the panelists, the adviser, and the committee of the RMMCERC, the researcher requested permission from the Schools Division Superintendent to conduct the study through a formal letter. The researcher then formalized the letter and mailed it to the school principals of the study's participating schools. The teachers involved in this study were oriented before administering the survey

questionnaire.

Authorship. The study's researcher is a graduate student at RMMC. Based on the comments and recommendations of her adviser, who had assisted the researcher while writing this thesis, she made several adjustments to her thesis. Under her researcher's direction, the paper may have been improved. Additionally, the researcher adhered to the norms established by the RMMC Ethics Review Committee for ethical consideration.

Results

This section presents the study's findings on the experiences, coping strategies, and insights of female teachers who are single parents. It also contains the participants' responses during the in-depth interview and focus group discussion.

3.1. Profile of the Participants

Participant 1 of the in-depth interview is named P1, 38 years old, is currently a teacher III in the Department of Education and has been serving the department for seventeen years. Participant 2, or P2, is a 51-year-old also a teacher II teaching grade nine students who has taught in the department for 26 years. In addition, Participant 3, or P3, is a 51-year-old teacher III and grade five adviser who has been teaching for 26 years. Furthermore, participant 4, or P4, is a 36-year-old Araling Panlipunan teacher who has been teaching for six years. Participant 5, or P5, is a 57-year-old teacher III teaching grade one pupil serving the Department of Education for 18 years.

On the other hand, participant 6, or P6, is 47-year-old teacher III who has been teaching Sarangan learners for 20 years. On the other hand, Participant 7, or P7, is a 52-year-old teacher III of grade 5 a SPED teacher who has been nurturing the young minds of the learners for 19 years now. Participant 8, or P8, is a 52-year-old teacher III teaching grade eight students and employed in DepEd Sarangani for 27 years. Additionally, Participant 9, or P9, is 43 years old, teaching senior high school, and has been teaching for 16 years. Participant 10, or P10, is a 43-year-old teacher who has taught in the Department of Education for 18 years.

Additionally, in the Focus Group Discussions, participant 11 is a 60-year-old master teacher who has been serving the department for 32 years and handling grade six learners. Participant 12, or P12, is a 34-year-old teacher III who has been teaching for nine years and handling grade five learners. Participant 13, or P13, is a 41-year-old teacher III, who has been nurturing young minds for 14 years and handling grade four learners. In addition, participant 14 is a 38-years-old master teacher II and has served DepEd Sarangani for 15 years. Additionally, participant 15, or P15, is 53-year-old master teacher III, who has been teaching for 27 years, handling grade five learners.

Consequently, participant 16, or P16, is a 59-year-old master teacher who has taught for 28 years, handling grade five SPED learners. Participant 17, or P17, is a 55-year-old master teacher who has been serving the DepEd for 33 years, handling grade five SPED learners. Participant 18, or P18, is 54-year-old teacher III who has taught in DepEd for 17 years, handling grade six learners. Participant 19 is a 58-year-old teacher III who has taught for 36 years and is now handling grade-five learners. Lastly, participant 20, or P20, is a 51-year-old master teacher who has taught for 13 years in the Department of Education.

All the participants are public school teachers in the Department of Education in the Municipality of Alabel, Province of Sarangani. Ten (10) participated in the in-depth interview, and another ten (10) participated in the focus group discussions.

Research 1: Teachers' View of Themselves as Female Single Parents

The study found four (4) emergent themes in teachers' views of themselves as female single parents. These are patiently taking responsibility, being good at managing time, experiencing financial instability, and becoming optimistic.

Patiently Taking Responsibilities

The first central theme that emerged from the experiences of the female single parents is patiently taking responsibility. When the teachers separated from their husbands, they assumed responsibility as fathers and mothers to their children. The teachers shared that there were instances when they felt restless about their responsibilities in their work, their children, and providing for their children's needs. The teachers have shared that they have performed multiple roles since their husbands left them.

The study on the Rights and Responsibilities of Parents supported the result, which revealed that the most frequently mentioned rights were being met.

The classroom teacher and the parents receive information about their children's achievements, transfer them to another school, and enroll them in the school. Nutrition, dressing, providing clothes and school uniforms, following their homework/lessons, helping with homework at home, directing them to social activities, and acquiring self-care skills were their children's most frequently repeated parental responsibilities. The teachers assumed that all the parents at their school were aware of their rights and asserted them (Kiral, 2019).

Restlessness about my responsibilities at home and in my work. One of the core ideas in the central theme of patiently taking responsibility is the responsibilities made by the teachers. The teachers felt restless when they performed their duties and responsibilities. They shared that they were living a different life when they were still with their husbands, providing the necessary

support in raising their children and providing all their needs. Their experiences as single parents are different. However, they also shared that they are doing everything possible to raise their children well and provide their nitty-gritty. The teachers shared that:

“So before since nagstart 2007, nagstart makikita ko sarili ko, I view myself as restless woman, *ika nga babaeng wlang pahinga*, pressured with so many obligations and responsibilities, stressful.” P1T1IDI; Lines 5-8

So, since 2007, when I started being a single parent, I have viewed myself as a restless woman. Many stressful obligations and responsibilities pressure me.

Participant 2 also stressed that:

“*Maliliit pa sila marami silang pangangailangan tanang pangangailangan una ng mga anak ko ako na ang naga shoulder so parang ano ang bigat parang krus araw araw kung dinadala ohh*” P2T2IDI; Lines 72-74

My children are still so young, and they still have many needs. I shouldered all of them, so I felt like it was a weighty responsibility. I feel like I am carrying a heavy cross every day.

In addition, participant 4 also mentioned that:

“*Tapos as a single parent pud nalisdan pud ko kay 3 years old ug 4 years old pa akong anak paghawa sa akong husband, so wala tapos akong family diari ako lng jud ang nagasupport.*” P4T4IDI; Lines 83-85

As a single parent, I find it difficult because I had my 3- and 4-year-old children when my husband left me. My family members are not here, so I must support them alone.

On the other hand, participant 11 mentioned that:

“*So cgro, me as cgro as participant 1 ahh... quite hard ang respobility kay daghan naman ta responsibilidad but then we need to cope up noh.. Face jud nato ni with all our mind, despite sa status in life and be blessed gyapon noh despite sa kakulangan kay as a solo parent we could be thankful gyapon sa mga naa ka, syempre with your kids at the same time life that you have mao rato.*” P11T11FGD; Lines 2-6

The responsibility is demanding, but I must cope because I have no choice. I must face it for my children, considering they also draw strength from me.

Additionally, participant 17 in the focus group discussion made mention that:

“For me, being a teacher at the same time single parents is not easy to handle dual responsibilities tapos naa pajud kay single parents dili jd basta basta noh.. dapat iset aside jud nato ang problema sa atong pamilya dili jud nato dal on mag atubang sa mga bata kay affected sila.” P17T17FGD; Lines 127-130

Being a teacher while being a single parent makes it work. Handling dual responsibility took work. It was never easy to become a single parent, and whatever problems they encountered, they had to leave them at home and not bring them to school.

Female teachers who are single parents have experienced a lot. They find being single parents challenging because they have a significant role in their family and work to attend to. Some even considered themselves restless women because of the responsibilities that started when their husbands left them.

Adjustments as a single mother, father, and teacher. Another core idea on the central theme of patiently taking responsibility is adjustments as a single mother. The teachers also played multiple roles as single parents. During the in-depth interview, they shared that they are performing the roles of mother and father to their children. They also find it challenging, especially when they are busy with their work and needed to attend to the needs of their children. The teachers shared that:

“Managing multiple responsibilities at once is quite challenging. It is difficult because I have a full workload in school, and at the same time, I also need to take care of my children and provide them with everything they need, including my time.” P2T2IDI; Lines 18- 21

Managing multiple responsibilities at once is quite challenging. I have a full workload in school, and at the same time, I also need to take care of my children and provide them with everything they need, including my time.

During the focus group discussion, participant 18 said that:

“Our role is vital in being a solo parent and a teacher. No matter how busy I get with teaching, including paperwork, I still get to check on my kids' activities/ lessons in school.” P18T18FGD; Lines 258-260

Our role is vital in being a solo parent and a teacher. No matter how busy I get with teaching, including paperwork, I still get to check on my kids' activities/ lessons in school.

Also, participant 20 mentioned that:

“Oh hmm.. the role of being a single parent in having multiple roles is doing two simultaneously. Teachers are difficult because both are equally important regarding priority.” P20T20FGD; Lines 263-265

Oh, hmm. Being a single parent means having multiple roles simultaneously. Teachers are difficult because both are equally important when it comes to priority.

Teacher 20 plays multiple roles as a single parent. She also finds it very challenging to balance her time between her work and her duties as a mother. After all, she has a full workload in teaching. She also needs to take care of her children.

Good in Managing Time

The second central theme in the experiences of the teachers who are single parents was that they are good at managing time. The teachers shared that they must balance their time well because they have many responsibilities. Their responsibilities towards their children, work, and careers made it difficult for them to manage their time well. They have also shared that they are practicing work-life balance.

The finding aligns with the results that by practicing time management, we can avoid disappointment in life. This disappointment could be monetary, professional, social, or other forms. We can avoid all these things if we make time for proper planning. Everything in our existence is powerless in the same way. It is pointless to give up one thing to achieve another. We will be disappointed if we amass enormous wealth but fail to maintain our health. However, successfully managing our time can avoid these setbacks (Chansaengsee, 2018).

Need to balance the time between life and work. The only core idea that emerged on the central theme of managing time is to balance the time between life and work. The teachers shared that they manage their time well between work and bonding with their children and other family members. They always ensure they give equal time to their work and their children. Moreover, a teacher made mention that:

“As a teacher, I also wake up at 3 am, ma'am, to prepare the needs of my children, to prepare food to prepare everything, and after them, that is the time that I also prepare for my work.” P1T1IDI; Lines 153-156

As a teacher, I wake up at 3 a.m. to prepare for my children's needs, food, and everything else. After that, I prepare for my work.

Participant 1 woke up at 3:00 in the morning to prepare the needs of her children for school, including their food and everything they needed. After she has prepared everything her children need, it was time to prepare for her needs. She has been balancing her time well. In addition, participant 2 also made mention that:

“Balancing time between work and duty as a single parent is more challenging; a perfect work-family balance can hardly be attained. For me, single parents should be flexible enough to attain an equilibrium between work and family” P2T2IDI; Lines 163-165

Balancing time between work and duty as a single parent is more challenging. A perfect work-family balance can hardly be attained. Single parents should be flexible enough to attain an equilibrium between work and family.

Participant 2 balances her time between her work and duty as a teacher. It was challenging for her because she had to manage her time well. However, a perfect work and family balance can hardly be attained, especially when they have many responsibilities. She also believed that single parents must be flexible enough to spend time with their family and work equally.

Also, participant 11 added during the focus group discussion that:

“Time management ang pinaka importante ah kabalo ka momanage sa imong pagka inahan, pagkaginikanan at the same time kabalo pud ka magmanage sa imong pagka maestra kay kung wala ka ana, of course dili nimo magampanan ug tarong ang imohang responsibilities.” P11T11FGD; Lines 172-175

Time management is essential because one must manage one's time between being a mother and teaching learners. Learning how to balance their time well would help them play both roles.

Experiencing Financial Instability

The third central theme in the experiences of female teachers who are single parents is financial instability. Since the teachers are single parents, they encounter financial instability despite having their regular job in the Department of Education. The teachers shared that they encountered problems in budgeting their salaries to provide for the needs and wants of their children. Financial-related obligations such as their loans and other obligations also caused them stress. This central theme has two core ideas: Budgeting problems and financial obligation-related pressure.

This central theme was supported by the findings that the role of a single parent is challenging, primarily when a woman leads the family. The issue of single mothers is linked to their children's upbringing, future, and setting down in life. Children are dependent on the single parent until they marry or get jobs. Following that, the problems are significantly reduced. To study the problems single mothers face, such as social, emotional, and economic issues, a sample of 50 single mothers was chosen using the snowball sampling

technique. The study's findings revealed that financial issues stressed most single mothers. The single mother's emotional life was also influenced by her status (Kotwal & Prabhakar, 2019).

Encountered budgeting problems. One of the core ideas under the significant theme of financial instability is budgeting problems. Since the teachers are single parents, they are not depending on their husbands in raising their children. Moreover, because their children have needs and wants, they also struggle with budgeting to meet their needs. The teachers shared that there were instances when they prioritized the needs of their children first rather than their own because of the tight budget.

"Mas inuuna ko talaga ang aking mga anak kasi minsan kailangan talaga tight ang budgeting para hindi mashort ang sahod." P8T8IDI; Lines 190-191

I prioritize my children's needs because sometimes, I need to be tight with my budget so that it will be sufficient to provide for their needs.

Participant 8 prioritized her children's needs. She always observes proper budgeting so that her salary will be enough to cater to all their needs. She spends her money on the essential needs of the family.

Financial obligation-related pressure. The teachers also felt pressured by their financial obligations. They have loans from the bank and other lending companies because they also finance the education of their children, especially those who are already in college. The teachers have no choice but to go to lending institutions, especially in emergencies, and they must act promptly. It has also caused them much pressure.

"My dream is to be financially stable, grow professionally despite my age, and keep updated on the educational challenges and changes. I want to be free from being tight in terms of budgeting" P2T2IDI; Lines 483-485

My dream is to be financially stable, to grow professionally despite my age, and to keep updated on the challenges and changes in education. I also want to be free from tight budgeting.

Participant 2 dreams of being financially stable and growing professionally despite her age. She also wants to be updated on the challenges and changes in education and dreams of seeking professional and personal development. She also wants to be free from tight budgeting and to be able to purchase all she wants to buy. Participant 4 also said that:

"For my children, I want them to be stable financially and...I do not want them to experience what I have experienced." P4T4IDI; Lines 497-498

I want my children to be financially stable, and I do not want them to experience what I have experienced.

Participant 4 dreams that her children will also be financially stable. She does not want her children to experience what she has experienced. She wants them to live a happy and prosperous life with regular work and a stable income to provide for all their needs and wants, especially in their future families.

On the other hand, during the focus group discussion, participant 14 also mentioned:

"When my husband left me, I had to support my children's needs all by myself. There are times that I got to apply for loans in the bank for emergency purposes." P14T14FGD; Lines 372-374

When my husband left me, of course, I had to support the needs of my children all by myself. There are times that I must apply for loans in the bank for emergency purposes.

Becoming Optimistic

The fourth central theme in the experiences of female single parents is becoming optimistic. The teachers shared that they remained positive about life despite their situation and the challenges they had encountered. They know there is a purpose in every problem they encounter, and they can surmount whatever trial life may give them.

Over the last 30 years, research into optimism and pessimism has grown exponentially. Many cross-sectional and longitudinal studies conducted during this time have found that optimism correlates with and predicts psychological and physical well-being, both in the presence and absence of stressors. Optimism has been linked to higher levels of self-esteem, positive mood, greater resilience to stressful or adverse events, self-mastery, active coping, illness prevention and stagnation, and recovery from illnesses, injuries, various types of surgery, and significant life events (Meevissen et al., 2018).

Despite the situation, positive outlooks should be manifested from us. A positive outlook is the only core idea in the central theme of becoming optimistic. The participants shared that being a single parent is always challenging. They must always double their time caring for their children and providing for all their needs. They might have encountered various challenges, but they remained positive in their outlooks. They have high hopes that everything would be fine in the future. On the other hand, participant 2 shared that:

But I am sure that at the end of the day, God will make all things beautiful if I do not get weary" P2T2IDI; Lines 317-318

However, I am sure God will make all things beautiful at the end of the day if I do not get weary.

Participant 4 also mentioned that:

“Nakacope ko yapon ko always lng gapray and think positive kung unsaon mn naku sa isip naku kung ifocus naku akong hunahuna sa iyaha maapektuhan akoang trabaho ug akong mga anak. .” P4T4IDI; Lines 29-31

I still coped with the situation, always praying to the Lord and thinking positively. The more I thought about my husband, the more my work and children would be affected.

Also, participant 2 said that:

“For me, challenges are part of my life. Everything happens for a reason. This belief of mine influenced me to manage my life, my children, and my pupils in any life situation with optimism” P2T2IDI; Lines 115-117

Challenges are part of my life. Everything happens for a reason. This belief has influenced me to manage my life, my children, and my pupils in any situation with optimism.

Despite the situation, it cannot be denied that the teachers still have a positive mindset. They were optimistic despite the challenges and difficulties they encountered. They even think that everything happens for a reason. They just prayed to the Lord and entrusted everything to Him.

Also, during the focus group discussion, participants 20 mentioned that:

“As a teacher and single parent, I must be strong enough to raise a happy family and healthy children, build positive relationships, and encourage them to behave positively.” P20T20FGD; Lines 64-66

As a teacher and single parent, I must be strong enough to raise a happy family and healthy children, build positive relationships, and encourage them to have positive behavior.

Also, participant 14 commented that:

“Ahh, I view my life as a single parent positively. I may face unending struggles in everyday life and the coming day, but this will not stop me from learning more about myself and how to cope with the different problems I encounter. As the saying goes, “Focus on the thing you can control makes me realize that life is what I make it.” P14T14FGD; Lines 16-20“

I view my life as a single parent positively. I may face unending struggles in everyday life and the coming day, but this will not stop me from learning more about myself and how to cope with my different problems. As the saying goes, “Focus on the thing you can control makes me realize that life is what I make it.”

Become happy in this stress-free life. Even though the teachers are experiencing various challenges as they live as single parents, participants have also shared that they are fulfilled because they have become stress-free. They are no longer thinking about their relationships with their husbands and enjoying giving their all to their children. Participant 8 shared that:

“However, it is delightful because I was able to fulfill my responsibilities as teacher and mother to my children” P8T8IDI; Lines 48-49

However, it is delightful because I could fulfill my responsibilities as a teacher and mother to my children.

On the other hand, participant 9 also mentioned that:

“Ahm... as a single parent or solo parent, life can sometimes be hard because you are trying to do everything yourself. On the other hand, it is also fulfilling in a way that makes it feel good to raise their children well even if they are alone.” P9T9IDI; Lines 50-53

Life can sometimes be challenging for a single or solo parent because they are trying to do everything themselves. However, it is also fulfilling because raising their children well feels good even when alone.

In addition, participant 3 also commented that:

“sa panahon nga solo parent ko hayahay interms nga wla koy husband na makig ilog sa akoang oras ang akong oras so akoang oras as time management nku dali lng kaayo imanage kay duha lng mn akong trabahuon pag- uli nku sa balay parent ko, pag abot nku sa eskwelahan teacher ko wla nkuy laing hunahunaon sama sa uban na maghunahuna nga naa pay bana nga atimanon.” P3T3IDI; Lines 169-174

As a single parent, I felt free because I no longer had my husband, who also demanded a specific amount of time from me. This time, I am free to do what I want, and I can decide independently. I only have two roles now: mother and teacher, and I no longer think of my responsibilities as a wife.

When they became single parents, the teachers felt free. They had only two roles to play, becoming a mother and a teacher, and no

longer thought of their responsibilities as wives. The teachers also felt fulfilled by raising their children well even though they were not receiving any support from their husbands. It was the teachers' fulfillment that they could provide for all their children's needs despite being alone.

Just avoid painful thoughts. The core idea that emerged on the theme of ignoring the pain is avoidance of painful thoughts. There are instances where the teachers can think of their experiences when they got separated from their husbands. Sometimes, they can feel how painful it is to be away from their husbands. However, they can only avoid thoughts that hurt them and focus on other things that need their attention.

"I'm not affected by something ahh... something loneliness. I have my work and have affected something; when I feel hurt, I ignore it. When others ask me what happened, I tell them I am okay. I also do not want others to worry more about my situation with my children. I must become an image of strength for them so that they will not be worried" P5T5IDI; Lines 87-91

I'm not affected by something like loneliness. I have my work, and I have affected something. When I feel like I am hurt, I ignore it. When others ask me what happened, I will tell them I am okay. I also do not want others to worry more about my situation with my children. I must become an image of strength for them so that they will not be worried.

In addition, participant 7 also mentioned that:

"Being a teacher is a blessing para sa ako kay with my profession nakatabang ni ug dako sa akua na dili ko maapektuhan sa pagbiya sa akoang bana sa amoa ug sa akong mga anak. Sakit man pero I will ignore it since my children depend on me all of their needs. I need to be strong and happy in front of my friends, family and my children in order for them not to worry my situation, but deep inside masakit kasi nasanay kana gusto mo na sana may kasama ka na magpalaki ng mga anak at kasama mong tumanda. Pero at end of the I need to be strong and accept the reality na wala na kami for the sake of my children to make them happy." P7T7IDI; Lines 95-100

Being a teacher is a blessing because my profession helped me a lot so that I would not be affected by my husband leaving us and my children. It hurts, but I will ignore it since my children defend me for all their needs. I need to be solid and happy in front of my friends, family, and even my children so they do not worry about my situation, but deep inside, it hurts because they are used to it. I wish I had someone to raise my children and grow old with. However, I need to be strong and accept that we are gone for the sake of my children to make them happy.

Participant 5 has been avoiding painful and negative thoughts to contain sharing positive vibes with her children and colleagues. When other people ask her about what happened, she tells them she is okay. She does not want others to worry about the situation, especially her children, because she always wants to become an image of strength for her children and those around her.

Table 1. Teachers' Value of Themselves as Female Single Parents

Clustered Themes	Emergent Themes
Restlessness about my responsibilities at home and in my work.	Patiently Taking Responsibilities
Patiently Taking Responsibilities	
Adjustments as a single mother, father and teacher.	Good at Managing Time
Need to balance the time between life and work.	
Encountered budgeting problems.	Experiencing Financial Stability
Financial obligation related.	
Despite the situation, positive outlooks should be manifested.	Becoming optimistic
Become happy in the stress-free-life.	
Just avoid painful thoughts.	

Research 2: Coping Mechanisms of Female Single Parent-Teachers

An in-depth interview and focus group discussion were conducted with twenty (20) informants to answer this research question. There were several sub-questions asked to draw out the coping mechanism experiences of female teachers who are single parents. Several emergent themes were identified: Overwhelming Support from Significant Others, Enriching One's Spirituality, Loving Oneself, Acceptance of Reality, Possessing a Stronger Personality, and Focusing on Responsibilities.

Overwhelming Support from Significant Others

The first central theme in the coping mechanisms of female teachers who are single parents is overwhelming support from significant others. The teachers shared that they receive much support from their family and friends. They felt that they were not alone in their battles. The only core idea that emerged in this central theme was assistance from family and friends.

This finding is corroborated by the idea that when it comes to identifying and accessing appropriate services for their child, parents may find child-serving systems (e.g., mental health, education, juvenile justice, child welfare, substance use treatment) to be complicated and overwhelming. Parent-peer support can assist these parents in more effectively navigating systems, learning from the experiences of other families, feeling less alone, and gaining hope, ideas, and information. This assistance can help parents meet the needs of their children more efficiently and with greater confidence and hope (Kutash et al., 2018).

Assistance from my family and friends. The first core idea that emerged on the coping mechanisms of the teachers is assistance from family and friends. The teachers shared that they could feel the efforts and love given by their family and friends. It lightens the burden they carry. The teachers also shared that they did not feel alone in their battles. Participant 1 shared that:

“Of course, mam ahh moral support of my parents’ mam o even *wla sila financial nga ginasupport sa akoa the moral support nga in times sa akoang bad experiences sa akoang problema nandyan sila advice to comfort me and advise me everything na hindi lng ko malugmok stand pa ako na magiging strong.*” P1T1IDI; Lines 202-205

Of course, ma'am, I received moral support from my parents. Even if they are not supporting me financially, they are always there to give their moral support, significantly when I am too affected by my problems. They gave me pieces of advice to make me even more robust.

On the other hand, participant 6 also shared that:

“And with the help of my family, co-teachers, and friends in terms of financial, advice, and moral support for us.” P6T6IDI; Lines 243-244

And with the help of my family, co-teachers, and friends in terms of financial, advice, and moral support.

Also, participant 14 said that:

“For me, first and foremost is the fervent prayer to our almighty God, trusting the whole process and his decision on why such a thing happened. Little by little, I was able to understand and came up strong the defeat. Second, the support coming from family and friends serves me strong.” P14T14FGD; Lines 286-289

For me, first and foremost is the fervent prayer to our almighty God, trusting the whole process and his decision on why such a thing happened. Little by little, I could understand and came up with a decisive defeat. Second, the support coming from family and friends serves me strong.

The teachers have received much support and help from their support system. Their family, colleagues, and friends gave them moral support, particularly when they were too affected by their problems. Their family gave them advice to make them even more robust and better.

Enriching One is Spirituality

The second central theme in the coping mechanisms of female teachers who are single parents is enriching one's spirituality. The parents are just praying to God for all their worries and problems. They just prayed for all the pain they felt and for the situation to get better the soonest time. They even noted that prayer had been their best weapon in facing various life trials, mainly when they dealt with problems with their husbands. This central theme has two core ideas: Constant Prayer and Trust with the Lord. The result is supported by the proposition that religion must serve a function that modernization does not. Understanding the role of religion in crisis and its persistence and socioeconomic consequences requires identifying who uses religion in crisis (Marzocchi, 2020).

Constantly pray for the situation to get better. The first core idea in the central theme is enriching one's spirituality. The teachers shared that they pray for all the problems they have encountered. They did not find single parenting an easy job. Still, they always prayed to the Lord that they would be given sufficient strength and determination to continue what they have started and forget all their pains. Participant 4 shared that:

“I always say “*kaya ra naku ni*” ang akong dakong pagsalig sa Ginoo maoy naghatag nakog kusog aron makabarog ko sa tanang pagsulay ug kalisod. Prayer is my best weapon in facing all the challenges in life.” P4T4IDI; Lines 229-232

I always tell myself that I can do this. My trust in the Lord gave me the strength to face the trials and difficulties in life. Prayer is my best weapon in dealing with and facing all the challenges in my life.

Also, participant 6 commented that:

“Hmmm. Prayer is the best way to help my children with all my problems and worries. I always render and ask God answers for my problems, and He answers them gradually.” P6T6IDI; Lines 241-243

Hmmm. Prayer is the best way to help my children with all their problems and worries. I always pray and ask God for answers to my problems, and He answers them gradually.

On the other hand, in the focus group discussion, participant 20 mentioned that:

“For me, prayers are one of the key reasons I remained strong despite all the trials. I have offered everything to the Lord because I know that in Him, nothing is impossible” P20T20FGD; Lines 316-318

For me, prayers are one of the key reasons why I remained strong despite all the trials. I have offered everything to the Lord because I know that in Him, nothing is impossible.

The teachers have been experiencing many problems, and their only partner in facing all these problems and challenges is their constant communication with the Lord through prayers. They mentioned that prayer is always the best way to answer various questions and solve specific problems.

Trusted the Lord and surrendered everything. The second core idea that emerged on the central theme of enriching one's spirituality is trust in the Lord. With all the problems the participants encountered, they surrendered it to the Lord. They believed they could do nothing without the guidance of the Almighty Father in heaven. Additionally, participant 8 mentioned that:

"Well, trust in God and learn from experience every time. I entrust everything to the Lord and surrender everything to Him. I know one day, it will all be fine." P8T8IDI; Lines 341-343

Well, for me, I trust in God and learn from experience every time. I entrust everything to the Lord and surrender everything to Him. I know that one day, it will all be okay.

On the other hand, focus group discussion participant 20 mentioned that:

"Everything that happens because I believe ah... Feel out for everything to happen because we have a purpose for my family and me. Then take courage, but courage will become God. Through God's grace, believe and trust in Him." P20T20FGD; Lines 394- 397

Everything that happens because I believe. Ahhh. Feel out for everything to happen because we have a purpose for my family and me. Then take courage, but courage will become God. Through God's grace, believe and trust in Him.

Also, participant 7 commented that:

"For me, prayers are one of the key reasons I remained strong despite all the trials. I have offered everything to the Lord because I know nothing is impossible in him, young family ko colleagues, and friends sila yong nagbibigay ng financial at moral support sa akin para makasurvive". P7T7FGD; Lines 306- 310

Prayers are one of the key reasons I remained strong despite all the trials. I have offered everything to the Lord because I know that in him, nothing is impossible. My family, colleagues, and friends provide financial and moral support to enable me to survive.

Participant 7 always entrusts everything, all her problems and worries, to the Lord Almighty. She surrenders everything to the Lord and believes that one day, all her problems would be solved, everything be fine and routine, and her family live happily together.

Loving Oneself

The third central theme in the coping mechanisms of female teachers who are single parents is loving oneself. The teachers shared that they always prioritize their self-worth above anything else. They were hurt, but it does not mean that they will allow themselves to be hurt forever. They learned to move on and move forward. The teachers also ensure that they rest sufficiently to remain healthy because their children need them, and they must remain strong for their children's sake. Two core ideas in this central theme are enough rest and self-motivation.

Self-love is an essential aspect of human life with personal and moral implications. It improves health and longevity by motivating people to strive for excellence and perfection; additionally, it allows people to conform to social norms and is even regarded as an essential force in the fight against terrorism. Researchers in psychology have approached this important topic in a variety of ways. Some researchers defined self-love as four self-relevant emotions (ashamed, humiliated, proud, and pleased), also called affective self-regard/self-love (Kruglanski et al., 2018).

Getting enough rest and maintaining a healthy lifestyle. The first core idea in the central theme of loving oneself is enough rest. The teachers have shared that being single parents entails many responsibilities for them. Thus, they always ensure enough rest to give their children and themselves ample time. They always ensure they give their children enough time for bonding, especially during weekends when they are not having classes. Consequently, participant 6 mentioned that:

"Certainly, I will not bring my problems into the classroom. When I feel like I have problems that are too heavy to carry and I felt tired, I take enough rest, and I bond with my children" P6T6FGD; Lines 292-295

Indeed, I will not bring my problems into the classroom. When I feel like I have problems that are too heavy to carry and I feel tired, I take enough rest, and I bond with my children.

Participant 6 brought only some of her problems and challenges to the classroom. She left them in the house and showed the other side of herself in the class because she did not want her performance in the class to be affected by the problems she encountered. She also gets enough rest whenever she feels tired. She even shared that she bonds with her children a lot.

Motivating oneself means things will get fine soon. The second core idea on the central theme of loving oneself is self-motivation. When the teachers encountered challenging situations wherein their strength and faith are being measured, they motivated themselves to continue to fight because many people still need them, especially their children. They kept on telling themselves that they could surpass any trial that came their way. Additionally, participant 2 shared that:

“So dili man jud malikayan nga every now and then naa jud moabot nga mga problema especially sa financial labi na kay tanan nakung mga anak nangiskwela na unya nagdungan pa gyud ang duha naku ka anak college so lisod jud kay ako lang isa nagsupport nila never ko me surrender. I always say “kaya ra naku ni” ang akong dakong pagsalig sa Ginoo maoy naghatag nakog kusog aron makabarog ko sa tanang pagsulay ug kalisod. I kept on motivating myself.” P2T2IDI; Lines 215-221

We cannot control our lives. There are instances where they will be put into tests, and problems are coming their way, especially financially, especially when all my children are in college already. I found it challenging to provide the necessary support, but I did not surrender. I always tell myself that I can do this. My trust in the Lord gives me the strength to stand from all the trials in life. I keep on motivating myself.

Participant 2 mentioned that there are times when her strength and faith are put to the test. Some problems come her way, especially regarding financial aspects, considering all her children are already enrolled in college. She finds it challenging to provide the necessary support, but she does not give up. Instead, she surrender everything to the Lord and continue to motivate herself that she could do it.

Acceptance of the Reality

The fourth central theme that emerged in the coping mechanism of the female teachers as they play their roles as single parents is acceptance of reality. The teachers can only fully move on and move forward if they have accepted the reality. During the interview I conducted, the teachers shared that as time passes by, they are also slowly accepting the reality, even if it hurts. It is the only way to free themselves from all their worries and the things that hurt them.

It is supported by the idea that acceptance is defined as "experiencing events fully and without defense, as they are," and can be measured by the degree of disagreement with statements such as "I try to distract myself when I feel unpleasant emotions" and "I tell myself that I should not have certain thoughts." Many mindfulness-based approaches are effective in treating adverse emotional reactions and troubling thoughts in psychotherapy settings, such as those found in GAD and depression (Baer, 2018).

Face the reality and accept it. The only core idea on the significant theme was acceptance of reality. Female single parents believe that they must face reality and accept the fact that their relationship with their husbands no longer works, and the only choice is to accept it. Some of the teachers shared that they would prefer facing reality to suffering from the pain they felt when they were together with their husbands. Participant 3 shared that:

“Sa akoang part mas dali lng tungod kay ang akoo man gud is ako man gud ang nagvolunteer na mahimong solo parent kay ako man nagpahawa sa akoang husband tungod kay nakita naku nga amoang panag uban dli naman maayo. So gipili nalang jud naku nga mas maayo pa na masolo parent. Maong dali rasad nako nadawat.” P3T3IDI; Lines 222-226

On my part, it was easy because I was the one who decided to become a single parent. I told my husband to leave the house because I felt like our relationship was no longer healthy. So, I chose to be a single parent because my work has been affected already. It was easy for me to accept the reality.

Moreover, participant 5 commented that:

“Yes, I manage to be strong and accept the reality. I seek support from my family and friends, who are my lifelines. Although it takes time to adjust slowly, I managed it step by step until it became a system. P5T5IDI; Lines 233-235

Yes, I manage to be strong and accept reality. I seek support from my family and friends, who are my lifelines. Although it takes time to adjust slowly, I managed it step by step until it became a system.

On the other hand, participant 8 mentioned that:

“Ahmmm. Well, I already accepted that I must face the day alone with children to attend to. To reduce extra- activities that may affect usage of my time.” P8T8IDI; Lines 249-251

Well, I already accepted that I need to face the day on my own with children to attend to, reducing extra activities that may affect the usage of my time.

The participants felt it was easy to adjust and accept reality. They had no choice because they already felt their relationships with their husbands were no longer healthy. They set their husbands free. Participant 8 became a single parent because the situation affected her work.

Possessing Stronger Personality

The fifth central theme that emerged in the coping mechanisms of the female teachers who are single parents as they play their respective roles is possessing a more assertive personality. The teachers shared that one of their coping strategies is to be stronger than they ever did before. Two core ideas emerged in this significant theme: strengthening oneself and courageously dealing with trials. Personality is a relatively stable precursor of behavior; it underpins a consistent way of thinking, feeling, and acting. On the other hand, personality is a predisposition to act or behave characteristically in response

to one's environment. Personal characteristics that account for consistent patterns of feeling, thinking, and behavior (Bleidorn et al., 2018).

Focusing on strengthening oneself. The only core idea that came out on the central theme of a more assertive personality is strengthening oneself. With all the trials and pains they encountered, one of the things they can do is to strengthen themselves. Participant 6 shared that:

“Although it takes time to adjust slowly, I was able to manage step by step until it became a system. Of course, I can choose what I want for my family.” P6T6DI; Lines 134-136

Although it takes time to adjust slowly, I managed step by step until it became a system. Of course, I can choose what I want for my family.

On the other hand, in focus group discussions, participant 14 shared that:

"As a single parent, you must compose yourself and be strong. Be the image of strength for their children and their family." P14T14FGD; Lines 187-188

As a single parent, they must compose themselves and be strong. Be the image of strength for their children and their family.

For the participant, it took time to adjust, but she managed until she was already used to it. She chose to do what was suitable for her and her children.

Focusing on the Responsibilities

The last central theme in the female teachers' coping mechanisms as they play their roles as single parents is focusing on the responsibilities. They think that they need to focus on their work and their responsibilities towards their children rather than focusing on the problems they have with their husbands and on dealing with their pain. It made their way towards moving on and moving forward easier. In their central theme, the only core idea was prioritizing the work.

Prioritize my responsibilities towards my children and my work. The only core idea that emerged on the central theme, which is focus, is to prioritize the work. The female teachers gave more priority to their work and the tasks that they played as single parents. Teachers need to focus on their work so that the situation will not affect their performance and duties. Teaching has been their bread and butter, which is why they are also giving much priority to their work. Participant 1 made mention that:

As a teacher naman of course I will play the role as a teacher na maibigay ko din ang nararapat para sa mga bata despite of my problems but of course my responsibility as duty as teacher also na dli pud madihado yong mga bata.” P1T1IDI; Lines 269-272

Of course, as a teacher, I will play the role of a teacher so that I can give what is due to my learners despite my problems. I will do my duties and responsibilities as a teacher so that my learners will not be affected.

Moreover, participant 4 added that:

“Ahh focus lng jud sa trabaho ug sa akong mga anak mao lng jud na akong gistrategy nga ginaahimo always focus sa trabaho kay kung dli ko magfocus unsa man akong ipakaon sa akong mga anak, tapos akong mga anak later sila pud nakaadjust nalng pud sila.” P4T4IDI; Lines 285-288

I just focused on my work and my children. That was the only strategy that I have used to always focus on my work because if I do not do it, I will not be able to provide food for my children. Later, my children also adjusted to the situation.

Indeed, female single-parent teachers have displayed the utmost resilience because they can still focus on their work as teachers despite their challenges and struggles. However, the teachers shared that they have no choice because if they do not do that, participants cannot provide food for their children, and they cannot provide all their needs. On the other hand, their children also learned to understand and adjust to the situation since they do not have a choice; instead, they faced it, show their mother their love, and persevere in their studies to make them proud.

Table 2. Coping Mechanism of Female Single Parent-Teachers

Clustered Themes	Emergent Themes
Assistance from my family and friends.	Overwhelming Support form Significant Others
Constantly pray for the situation to get better.	
Trusted the Lord and surrendered everything.	Enriching One is Spirituality
Getting enough rest and maintaining a healthy lifestyle.	Loving Oneself
Motivating oneself means things will get fine soon.	
Face reality and accept it.	Acceptance of the Reality
Focusing on strengthening oneself.	Possessing Stronger Personality
Prioritize my responsibilities towards my children and my work.	Focusing on the responsibilities

Research 3: Insights of Female Single Parent-Teachers

An in-depth interview and focus group discussion were conducted to answer this research question. Various sub-questions were asked to draw out the insights the female single parent-teacher could share based on their experiences. The study found six (6) significant themes that emerged: resiliency, Feeling the Pain Until it Hurts No More, Never Forgetting to Pray, Facing Life Positively, Managing Finances Well, and Being an Inspiration.

Resilience is the Key to Moving Forward

The first central theme from the female single-parent teachers' insights is resiliency. During the in-depth interview, the teachers encouraged others in the same situation to be resilient and vital for their children. They urged everyone to maintain a strong personality while dealing with the situation. The core idea in this significant theme is never to give up.

It is corroborated by the idea that the ability to adapt successfully in the face of stress and adversity is called resilience. Stressful life events, trauma, and chronic adversity can have a significant impact on brain function and structure, leading to the development of posttraumatic stress disorder (PTSD), depression, and other psychiatric disorders. However, most people do not develop such illnesses after stressful life events and are thus considered resilient (Tang et al., 2018).

Never give up on the trials and challenges I have faced. The only core idea that came out on the significant theme was resiliency. The teachers shared that there are instances when they wanted to quit and surrender because of the situation, but they were reminded to fight because their children are still looking up to them. They have also realized that they should never give up on the situation and can eventually move forward toward living a fruitful life with their children. In addition, participant 1 shared that:

"Do not give up whatever problems you encounter. Fight for the sake of their children. Love their children the best as they can. Do not be discouraged; stand up for their children need them" P1T1I1D1; Lines 393-395

Please do not give up whatever problems they encounter. Fight for the sake of their children. Love their children the best they can. Do not be discouraged; stand up for the children who need them.

Moreover, participant 2 mentioned that:

"All I can give or share to my fellow female single parents is to keep fighting; if you feel tired, just rest, and after that, continue to face those challenges because I believe that challenges would make you stronger, so at the end of the day tell yourself "I made it!" P2T2I2D1; Lines 432-435

All I can give or share to my fellow female single parents is to keep fighting; if they feel tired, rest, and then continue to face those challenges because I believe they will make them stronger, so at the end of the day, tell yourself, "I made it.

Furthermore, participant 5 commented that:

"Let peace be in your family and set humility and peace with the past. Stay organized, immediately gather themselves, and set their plan and goals. Be proud, stand upright, and do not allow loneliness and guilt to succumb to them. Be resilient when they want to give up; think of their children; they need them." P5T5I5D1; Lines 408-411

Let peace in their family, humility, and peace with the past. Stay organized, immediately gather themselves, and set plans and goals. Be proud, stand upright, and do not allow loneliness and guilt to succumb to them. Be resilient when they want to give up and think of their children; they need them.

The teachers' resilience was displayed in their answers during my in-depth interview. The teachers urged other female single parents to fight and stand up for their children. They also shared that they rested whenever single parents got tired. When they want to give up, they thought of their children, who also drew strength and inspiration from them.

Feeling the pain Until it Hurts No More

The second central theme that emerged from the insights the female teachers could share based on their experiences is feeling the pain until it hurts no more. The teachers were hurt because of the situation; they could not accept that their family would no longer compete. However, the teachers just endured the pain and recognized it until the time came that it no longer hurt them. One core idea under this significant theme is accepting reality.

This sensation is supported by the fact that pain is more than just a physical sensation; it is also psychological, emotional, and biological. These factors influence how intensely people experience pain, how debilitating the pain is, and how effective treatment is likely to be. Individuals differ significantly in their ability to regulate emotions, including emotional reactions to pain. According to studies, some patients appear more sensitive to pain than others. Even under laboratory conditions, where the intensity of a pain-inducing stimulus can be controlled, patient response varies greatly (Karos et al., 2018).

Learning to accept reality to be free from pain. The only core idea in the central theme is feeling the pain until it hurts no more is accepting the reality. The female teachers admitted that they were hurt when their husbands left them. They could hardly move on

during that time. However, their pain vanished when they accepted and faced reality, especially when they realized they did not deserve it. Additionally, participant 9 shared that:

“Ahmm... everyday give time to your family, have bonding, and ipafeel jud nimo ang love sa ilaha kay para time will come if one of you left, dili ka magmahay although sakit kaayo. In terms of the pain, recognize it... Feel it. later, you will realize that you don't deserve to be hurt.” P9T9IDI; Lines 459-462

Ah, it would help if they gave time to their family daily. Bond with them and let them feel loved so that if one decides to leave, they will have no regrets. In terms of the pain, recognize it. Feel it. Later, they will realize that they do not deserve to be hurt.

Participant 9 shared that pain is normal. When they feel pain, they must recognize it and feel it. Eventually, they realized that they are not worth the pain and do not deserve to be hurt.

In addition, participant 16 added that:

“In my case, I just let the pain go away. As time passes by, they will forget the pain they have felt. Furthermore, when that happens, they can be happy again.” P16T16FGD; Lines 379-380

In my case, I just let the pain go away. As time passes by, they will forget the pain they have felt. Moreover, when that happens, they can be happy again.

Never Forget to Pray

The third central theme that emerged from the insights of the female teachers who are single parents regarding their experiences is asking for God's Guidance. The teachers shared that they prayed when worried about the situation and doubted if they could surpass all the trials they encounter, including the pains participants have felt. It has been their armor in battling against life's challenges. In this central theme, there is only one core idea: asking for God's guidance.

Asking for God's guidance. The only core idea under the significant theme of never forgetting to pray is asking for God's guidance. They ask for God's guidance mainly when they deal with their problems and are tasked to decide about something. They ask God's help when there are times that they are put into tests. Furthermore, participant 3 shared that:

ah Piece of advice unang una mangadji lng jud tagunit sa ginoo and then. ask guidance from Him” P3T3IDI; Lines 400-401

Ah, a piece of advice is to pray to the Lord and ask for guidance from Him.

Also, participant 5 added that:

“Beyond the clouds, the sun is still shining. Just pray for God's divine providence. When they must make decisions, for and seek guidance from the Lord” P5T5IDI; Lines 376-378

Beyond the clouds, the sun is still shining. When they must make decisions and seek guidance from the Lord, pray for God's divine providence.

On the other hand, focus group discussion participant 6 also mentioned that:

“tapos ano lng pud iampo lng pud nato pag abot sa panahon nga magmalampuson atong mga anak uban manta sa kalampusan sa atong mga anak.” P6T6FGD; Lines 435-437

Then, let us also pray that our children will succeed in their lives because we are also part of that.

The female teachers said they have been praying for God's help when encountering problems. However, in this section, the female single-parent teachers emphasized the need for them to ask guidance from the Lord when they have to make decisions for their family and pray that success be granted to their children because they are also part of that success.

Face Life Positively

The fourth central theme in the insights of female teachers who are single parents regarding their experiences is to face life positively. The teachers shared that there are many trials as they play their roles as single parents. However, it would help if they stayed optimistic, and they must face each day positively. They believe that each new day brings new hope and new beginnings. The only core idea in this significant theme is to focus on the positive side.

For a long time, the concepts of optimism and pessimism have been recognized. Their use in modern psychology can be traced back to the 17th century, at the start of the modern period of philosophy. Philosophers at the time commonly held that the successful application of rationalization of the cosmos required either an optimistic or pessimistic philosophical outlook. These perspectives were seen as opposing positions regarding the universe: either favorable to human goals and aspirations or generally hostile to the flourishing of humans and civilizations (Khosla, 2021).

Focusing on the positive side of life. The only core idea in the central theme of facing life is to focus on the positive side. They remained

optimistic with all the negativities the teachers have encountered and the trials they have surpassed. It is also one of the things that they wanted to share with all the single parents. With this, participant 2 shared that:

“Those experiences not only taught me how to endure hardship but also to face life situations positively. Moreover, I would like to share this with other single parents.” P2T2IDI; Lines 398-399

Those experiences taught me not only how to endure hardship but also how to face life situations positively. Moreover, I would like to share this with other single parents.

Additionally, participant 10 mentioned that:

“Life is full of negativities, so always share positive vibes with others despite your situation.” P10T10IDI; Lines 422-423

Life is entire of negativities, so always share positive vibes with others despite their situation.

Also, participant 12 stated that:

“Instead of focusing on the negative side of the situation, learn to embrace the positive one and draw strength from it.” P12T12FGD; Lines 468-470

Instead of focusing on the negative side of the situation, learn to embrace the positive one and draw strength from it.

The teachers focused more on the positive things that happened instead of dwelling on the negative thoughts. They think life is full of negativities, so they must always bring positive vibes and share them with others despite their situation.

Managing Finances Well

The fifth central theme in the insights that female teachers who are single parents can share with other people is managing finances well. The teachers shared that single parents must ensure their children's needs and wants are provided. They prioritize the needs of their children, especially in terms of their studies, since some of the teachers already have children who are college students. They also advised other single parents to manage their finances well because they must save for their children's future. On the other hand, there is only one core idea in this central theme: to be wise in budgeting.

Furthermore, this finding is supported by the idea that while people have much more money today than they did generations ago, financial experts agree that the amount of knowledge on managing that money has not kept pace. Taking charge of our financial planning and management and implementing it is critical for every individual. We must learn how to manage our money. It is to establish our household budget, save for the future, plan for our retirement, and invest for a brighter future. It is also important because everyone wants to be debt-free and only work once old to survive and educate their children (Prihartono & Asandimitra, 2018)

Always being wise in terms of budgeting the finances. The only core idea that emerged on the central theme of managing finances well is to be wise in budgeting. The female single parent-teachers advise other single parents to be wise in budgeting their money, especially since they have many responsibilities. The teachers also mentioned that they see to it that their salaries are spent well by ensuring that the family's needs are met. In addition, participant 8 stated that:

“*Financial management kung paano nmu imanage sweldo na dapat mogasto ta dli beyond sa atong sweldo so ideas lng na pwd nku ishare sa mga parent is pugong jud ta kinahanglan mag abot jud ang both ends sa atoang panginahanglan sa atong sweldo.*” P3T3IDI; Lines 365-369

It would help if they managed their salary well. They need not spend more than they earn, so let us be tight when it comes to our budgeting so that our salary will be enough to cater to our needs.

Furthermore, participant 7 also mentioned that:

“It is never easy to budget our salary for our own needs and the needs of our children, especially since we already have our college students. Thus, we need to spend our money well and be wise in spending.” P7T7IDI; Lines 382-384

Budgeting our salary for our and our children's needs is always challenging, especially since we already have college students. Thus, we need to spend our money wisely.

The teachers shared that single parents should always manage their finances well. They must be tight when it comes to budgeting their resources. They should prioritize the family's basic needs and ensure they spend only what they have earned.

Be an Inspiration

The last central theme of the insights that female teachers who are single parents could share with others is to be an inspiration. With all the trials and difficulties the teachers have encountered, they have already proven their strength and resilience as human beings. Thus, they want to share this with other single parents as well. During the in-depth interview, they shared that the teachers could inspire other people, especially their children. Two core ideas in this central theme are motivating children and fulfilling dreams.

Always motivate the children to be good. The first core idea on the central theme of being an inspiration is to motivate children. During the in-depth interview, the teachers shared that single parents' lives may inspire their children to do better in their studies and reach their wildest dreams. It may also motivate the children to do good towards others and respect others. Further, participant 7 commented that:

“Be a motivating factor to your children. Please do not allow them to be filled with negativities about their lives. Let them appreciate that despite the situation, they are still blessed.” P7T7FGD; Lines 444-446

Be a motivating factor to children. Please do not allow them to be filled with negativities about their lives. Let them appreciate that despite the situation, they are still blessed.”

The teachers highlighted that single parents may always serve as motivating factors towards their children and that parents should not allow their children's lives to be filled with negativities. One thing parents should inculcate in the minds of their children is the idea that despite the situation, they are still blessed and fortunate to have a mother who gives them time, love, and support wholeheartedly.

Fulfilling dreams despite all the challenges. The last core idea in the central theme of being an inspiration is fulfilling dreams. The teachers shared during the interview that other single parents can still pursue their dreams despite being single. They can still achieve all the things that they wanted despite the situation. During the focus group discussions, participant 8 mentioned that:

together with my children. No worries, I enjoy life to the fullest despite my challenges and difficulties. I wanted to fulfill my dreams and ambition to be accurate and successful". P8T8FGD; Lines 600-603

"My dream for myself is to be happy together with my children. No worries; enjoy life to the fullest despite my challenges and difficulties. I want to fulfill my dreams and ambitions to be accurate and successful.

Also, participants 5 commented that:

"Let's make our life ahh... fulfill our dreams in our life, let not anyone na ano *ni what is this magtambag sa inyong mga dreams noh*.Despite the situation, reach their dreams and ambition in life." P5T5FGD; Lines 586-589

Let us make our lives fruitful. Let us fulfill our dreams in life, and do not let anyone hinder us from reaching them. Despite the situation, they reach their dreams and ambitions in life.

Participant 5 highlighted the idea that single parents should not settle for less. They should also have their dreams and turn them into reality. They should not let anyone hinder them from reaching their aspirations in life. They deserve to have a dream despite the situation and should do their best to reach and achieve it.

Table 3. *Insights of Female Single Parent-Teachers*

<i>Clustered Themes</i>	<i>Emergent Themes</i>
Never give up on the trials and challenges have faced.	Resiliency
Learning to accept the reality to be free from pain.	Feeling the pain until it hurts no more.
Asking for God's guidance	Never forget to pray.
Focusing on the positive side of life.	Face Life Positively
Always being wise in terms of budgeting the finances.	Managing Finances well.
Fulfilling dreams despite all the challenges.	Be an Inspiration

Discussion

This section presents a discussion of the results and findings of the study on the experiences of female teachers who are single parents, their coping mechanisms, and the insights that they can share with others. The implications for practice, future research, and concluding remarks were also discussed in this part.

Teachers view themselves as female single parents.

When they shared their experiences as single parents, the teachers shared various challenges, struggles, and the positive sides of single parenting. They voiced their feelings and emotions when the researcher conducted the in-depth interview. When the researcher analyzed the data, four (4) emergent themes emerged in the participants' experiences: patiently taking responsibility, Good Time management, Experiencing Financial Instability, and Becoming Optimistic.

Two core ideas emerged in the first central theme, Patiently taking responsibility: restlessness about her home responsibilities and adjustments as a single mother, father, and teacher. Parental Rights and Responsibilities. The rights most frequently mentioned are to meet with class teachers and parents, receive information about their child's performance, transfer their child to another school, and enroll them in the school. Children's most frequently repeated parental responsibilities were feeding, dressing, providing clothing and uniforms, observing homework and classes, helping with homework at home, supervising social activities, and developing self-care skills. Teachers assumed that all parents at school were aware of their rights and claimed them (Kiral, 2019).

Also, one core idea emerged in the second central theme that was good in managing time: The need to balance the time between life

and work. They can avoid disappointments in life by managing their time. This disappointment can take financial, professional, social, or other forms. It can be avoided if they take their time and plan appropriately. All our beings are equally helpless. It makes no sense to give up something to achieve something else. It would be unpleasant if they were to amass a great fortune and not maintain their health. However, time management can avoid these setbacks (Chansaengsee, 2018).

Furthermore, in the third central theme, experiencing financial instability, there were two core ideas: encountering budgeting problems and financial obligation-related pressure. The role of a single parent is challenging, especially when a woman heads the family. The issues of single mothers relate to the upbringing of their children, their future, and their lives. Children depend on a single parent until they get married or find work. It dramatically reduces the problem. Her sample of 50 single mothers was selected using a snowball sampling technique to explore the issues facing single mothers, including social, emotional, and financial problems. The study found that financial problems stress the majority of single mothers. Her single status also affected a single mother's spiritual life (Kotwal & Prabhakar, 2019).

In addition, in the last central theme, which is becoming optimistic, there were only three core ideas: despite the situation, positive outlooks should be manifested, becoming happy in this stress-free life, and avoiding painful thoughts. Several cross-sectional and longitudinal studies conducted during this period have found that optimism correlates with and predicts psychological and physical well-being, with or without stressors. Optimism is associated with higher levels of self-esteem, positive mood, greater resilience to stress and adverse events, self-control, positive coping, disease prevention and stagnation, illness, injury, various types of surgery, and recovery from significant life events (Meevissen et al., 2018).

Furthermore, the researcher wants to become happy in this stress-free life. Mothers are the primary caretakers of their children and play an essential role in their education. The first madrasah occurs at home, and the mother is the best teacher for a child. Moreover, her mission will be accomplished if she raises her children (Oluwayemisi et al., 2018).

Lastly, avoid painful thoughts. Various psychological factors influence pain perception. Two factors involved in normal psychological processes are paying attention to noxious stimuli and interpreting them as pain. Of course, pain is a subjective experience and undoubtedly related to physiological processes, but how people respond to new pain episodes is shaped and influenced by previous experiences. Learning from experience is necessary to manage pain and stay healthy. These psychological processes are, therefore, crucial for survival (Vlaeyen & Crombez, 2020).

Coping mechanisms of the female single parent-teachers.

During the in-depth interview, the researcher also asked the female teachers how they coped with their experiences, especially their challenges and struggles. Six (6) primary themes emerged: overwhelming support from significant others, enriching one's spirituality, loving oneself, accepting reality, possessing a more assertive personality, and focusing on responsibilities. In the first central theme, overwhelming support from significant others, there was only one core idea: assistance from family and friends. Parents can find the parenting system (mental health, education, juvenile justice, child welfare, drug treatment) complex and overwhelming when it comes to finding and accessing the right services for their children. Peer support for parents helps them navigate the system more effectively, learn from other family members' experiences, feel less alone, and gain hope, ideas, and information. This support helps parents meet their children's needs more efficiently, with more confidence and hope (Kutash et al., 2018).

The second central theme was enriching one's spirituality. Two core ideas were constant prayer for improving the situation, trusting the Lord, and surrendering everything. This result is supported by the thesis that religion must fulfill a function that modernization cannot. It is necessary to identify who uses religion in crisis to understand the role of religion in crisis, its survival, and its socioeconomic impact (Marzocchi, 2020).

On the other hand, in the third central theme, which was loving oneself, there were two core ideas: getting enough rest, maintaining a healthy lifestyle, and motivating oneself. Things will get fine soon. Loving oneself is an essential aspect of human life and has personal and moral implications. Health and longevity are improved by motivating people to strive for excellence and perfection. Moreover, it enables adaptation to social norms and is even considered a significant force in the fight against terrorism. Psychological researchers have approached this vital subject in a variety of ways. Some researchers define narcissism as four self-related emotions (embarrassment, humiliation, pride, and joy), also called emotional self-esteem/narcissism (Kruglanski et al., 2018).

Also, in the fourth central theme, acceptance of reality, there was only one core idea: face and accept reality. Acceptance is defined as "to experience an event as it is, unprotected fully" and can be measured by the level of dissatisfaction with statements such as "trying to distract yourself when you feel uncomfortable" or "telling yourself thoughts you should not be thinking." Several mindfulness-based approaches are effective in treating adverse emotional reactions and troublesome thoughts in psychotherapeutic situations, such as those encountered in GAD and depression (Baer, 2018).

Furthermore, in the fifth central theme, possessing a more assertive personality, there was only one core idea: focusing on strengthening oneself. Lastly, in the last central theme, focusing on responsibilities, there was only one core idea: prioritize responsibilities towards children and work. Personality is a relatively stable precursor to behavior. It supports a consistent way of thinking, feeling, and acting. Conversely, personality can be defined as the disposition to act or behave characteristically, depending

on the environment. Individual traits are involved in consistent patterns of feeling, thinking, and behavior (Hopwood, 2018).

Insights of the female single parent-teachers.

The third research question focused on the insights of female teachers who are also single parents. These insights were based on their overall experiences. During the interview, the researcher asked them open-ended questions. After analyzing the data, six (6) significant themes emerged: resiliency, feeling the pain until it hurts no more, never forgetting to pray, facing life positively, managing finances well, and being an inspiration.

For first central theme resiliency; there was only one core idea: never give up on the trials and challenges they have faced. Resilience is the capacity to adjust effectively in the face of stress and hardship. Stressful life experiences, trauma, and ongoing hardship can significantly impact a person's brain's structure and function. It can result in the development of mental diseases such as depression and post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD). However, most people are resilient and do not develop such illnesses after stressful life events (Tang et al., 2018).

On the other hand, the second central theme is feeling the pain until it hurts no more; there was only one core idea: learning to accept the reality to be free from pain. Pain is not just a physical sensation. It is also psychological, emotional, and biological. These factors influence how much pain people experience, how debilitating pain is, and how effective treatment is. People vary greatly in their ability to regulate emotions, including their emotional response to pain. Studies show that some patients are more sensitive to pain than others. Even under laboratory conditions where the intensity of noxious stimuli can be controlled, patient responses vary widely (Karos et al., 2018).

Also, in the third significant theme, never forgetting to pray, there was only one core idea: asking for God's guidance. Moreover, in the fourth central theme of facing life positively, there was only one core idea: focusing on the positive side of life. The concepts of optimism and pessimism were recognized. Its use in modern psychology can be traced back to the 17th century, the beginning of the modern era of philosophy. Philosophers of the time generally believed that the successful application of cosmic rationalization required an optimistic or pessimistic philosophical attitude. These perspectives were seen as opposing positions regarding the universe. It is either sympathetic to human purposes and aspirations or hostile to the flourishing of people and civilizations (Khosla, 2021).

Furthermore, in the fifth central theme, managing finances well, there was only one core idea: always being wise in budgeting finances. Lastly, in the last central theme, inspiration, there were two (2) core ideas: always motivate the children to be good and fulfill dreams despite challenges. Financial experts agree that people have far more money today than generations ago, but the level of knowledge about managing that money needs to catch up. Everyone must take responsibility for executing financial planning and management. We must learn how to manage money. It is not just about building a family budget but also about saving for the future, planning for retirement, and investing in a better future. It is also because everyone wants a debt-free life rather than working into old age to survive and ensure an education for their children (Prihartono & Asandimitra, 2018).

4.1. Implications for Practices

Various significant themes emerged after carefully analyzing and interpreting the data gathered from the participants.

Teacher views themselves as female single parents.

Patently Taking Responsibilities. School administrators may acknowledge female single-parent teachers' remarkable patience in managing their responsibilities. Providing additional support and understanding in areas such as flexible deadlines and professional development can help these educators balance their dual roles. Recognizing their commitment and creating a supportive environment can enhance their ability to address their students' diverse needs patiently.

Good in Managing Time. School heads may support these teachers by offering tools and training in efficient classroom management techniques and scheduling flexibility. It not only aids their professional performance but also contributes to a healthier work-life balance, ultimately benefiting the entire school community.

Experiencing Financial Instability. The Department of Education may offer financial wellness programs, salary advancements, and emergency financial support that can alleviate some of their burdens. Additionally, providing information on grants and scholarships for further education and professional development can empower these teachers to enhance their qualifications and secure better financial stability, contributing to their overall well-being and effectiveness in the classroom.

Becoming Optimistic. School administrators may nurture this positivity by creating a supportive, inclusive culture that celebrates their achievements and provides mental health resources. Encouraging an optimistic outlook enhances the teachers' well-being and positively influences the students they teach.

Coping mechanisms as female single-parent- teachers

Overwhelming support from Significant Others. School administrators may encourage a community culture that recognizes and appreciates the positive impact of solid support networks on female single-parent teachers. By facilitating flexible working hours and encouraging family-friendly events, administrators can help these educators balance their responsibilities and leverage the

overwhelming support from their significant others, enhancing their overall well-being and effectiveness in their roles.

Enriching One's spirituality. To support female single-parent teachers in enriching their spirituality, school administrators may provide opportunities for quiet reflection and meditation within the school environment. Additionally, offering access to counseling services and creating a supportive, inclusive atmosphere where diverse spiritual practices are respected can help these teachers find balance and inner peace, positively influencing their professional lives.

Loving Oneself. School heads may promote self-care among female single-parent teachers by encouraging participation in wellness programs and providing physical and mental health resources. Creating an environment emphasizing the importance of self-love and self-care can help these teachers maintain their well-being, leading to greater job satisfaction and effectiveness in the classroom.

Acceptance of Reality. School administrators may support female single-parent teachers in accepting their reality by fostering an empathetic and understanding school culture. Offering professional counseling services, peer support groups, and realistic expectations regarding workloads can help these educators navigate their personal and professional challenges more effectively, allowing them to focus on their strengths and contributions.

Possessing a Stronger personality. School heads may provide leadership and professional development opportunities that allow these educators to showcase and further develop their strong personalities, recognizing the resilience and strength of female single-parent teachers. Acknowledging their unique perspectives and experiences can enrich the school community and empower these teachers to become role models and leaders.

Focusing on the Responsibilities. To help female single-parent teachers focus on their responsibilities, administrators may implement clear communication channels and provide organizational tools that streamline their tasks. By reducing unnecessary bureaucratic burdens and offering support staff, administrators can enable these teachers to concentrate on their primary duties, ultimately enhancing their productivity and job satisfaction.

Insights of female single-parent teachers.

Resiliency. School administrators may recognize and support the resiliency of female single-parent teachers by providing professional development opportunities focused on stress management and resilience-building. Offering mentoring programs and peer support groups can also help these teachers share their experiences and strategies for overcoming challenges, fostering a stronger, more supportive school community.

Feeling the pain Until it Hurts No More. To support female teachers who are single parents in healthily managing their grief and emotions, school administrators may give access to counseling and support groups as well as other mental health services. Creating a compassionate and understanding work environment where teachers feel safe expressing their feelings can facilitate healing and personal growth, enabling them to focus on their professional responsibilities better.

Remember to Pray. It is crucial to respect and accommodate the spiritual practices of female single-parent teachers. Administrators may designate quiet spaces for prayer and meditation within the school and ensure that teachers have the flexibility to observe their spiritual routines. This support can help these educators maintain their spiritual well-being, which can positively impact their professional lives.

Face Life Positively. To encourage a positive outlook, school administrators should celebrate the achievements and contributions of female single-parent teachers. Providing opportunities for professional growth, recognizing their hard work, and fostering a positive school culture can help these educators face life's challenges with optimism and confidence, benefiting their personal and professional lives.

Managing Finances Well. Administrators may assist female single-parent teachers in managing their finances by offering financial literacy workshops and providing information on available financial aid and resources. Additionally, advocating for fair compensation and benefits can help alleviate financial stress, allowing these teachers to focus more effectively on their roles and responsibilities.

Be an Inspiration. School heads may highlight their stories and achievements through newsletters, events, and recognition programs. By showcasing their resilience and dedication, these teachers can inspire others within the school community to overcome obstacles and strive for excellence.

Conclusion

The researcher could not imagine how hard the lives of female single parents were until the researcher listened to and understood their experiences, struggles, and resilience in dealing with all of these. The researcher was amazed at the strength the female single parents exhibited as they played their roles as teachers and single parents. They have played their roles well despite the adversities they are facing. Their positive outlooks made them successful in combatting all the challenges and struggles they encountered along the way.

The researcher was motivated to conduct this study because the researcher has friends who are single parents and have listened to their stories. They are teachers in the public schools in our division. The researcher found it interesting, so the researcher conducted a study

on it so that their rich experiences and voices could also be heard. The researcher is not a single parent, but the researcher was motivated to conduct this study for her friends who are single parents- for this could pave the way for the Department of Education to develop mechanisms to aid their teacher's parents.

Conducting this study made the researcher realize how hard it is for teachers to play their roles as female single parents. However, their love towards their family, especially their children, drove them to surpass every trial that came their way. During the in-depth interview, the researcher tends to become emotional listening to the stories, especially with those teachers who are already about to retire. They were so proud because they successfully raised their children despite the absence of their husbands. Their stories must be unleashed, for this may inspire teachers in different parts of the world.

The researcher learned a lot from the experience of the female teachers who are single mothers. Some are also experiencing challenges. Therefore, the Department of Education should provide programs that would empower teachers who are single parents and provide employees with wellness programs in the academe. In this way, the female teachers would feel that they are well-supported.

References

- Abalos, J. (2017). Divorce and separation in the Philippines: Trends and correlates. *Demographic Research*, 36, 1515-1548. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/26332173>
- Abramovitz, M. (2017). *Regulating the lives of women: Social welfare policy from colonial times to the present*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315228150>
- Arditti, J., Molloy, S., Spiers, S., & Johnson, E. (2019). Perceptions of nonresident father involvement among low-income youth and their single parents. *Family Relations*, 68(1), 68-84. <https://doi.org/10.1111/fare.12346>
- Assaad, R., Hendy, R., Lassassi, M., & Yassin, S. (2020). Explaining the mena paradox: Rising educational attainment, yet stagnant female labor force participation. *Demographic Research*, 43, 817. <https://doi.org/10.1111/fare.12346>
- Azhari, A., Leck, W., Gabrieli, G., Bizzego, A., Rigo, P., Setoh, P., & Esposito, G. (2019). Parenting stress undermines mother-child brain-to-brain synchrony: A hyper scanning study. *Scientific Reports*, 9(1), 11407. <https://doi.org/10.1111/fare.12346>
- Baer, H. (2018). Redoing feminism: Digital activism, body politics, and neoliberalism. In *Digital Feminisms* (pp.25-42). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315406220>
- Bandura, A. (2010). The social learning theory of aggression. In *The War System* (pp. 141-156). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781412959193.n17>
- Barone, J., "How the law fails single mothers" (2017). Law School Student Scholarship763. https://scholarship.shu.edu/student_scholarship/763
- Bhat, N., & Patil, R. (2019). Single parenthood families and their impact on children in India. *Delhi Psychiatry Journal*, 22(1), 161-165. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/334203977_Single_parenthood_families_and_their_impact_on_children_in_India
- Bleidorn, W., Hopwood, C. & Lucas, R. (2018). Life events and personality traitchange. *Journal of Personality*, 86(1), 83-96. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315406220>
- Bowlby, J. (1979). The Bowlby- Ainsworth attachment theory. *Behavioral and brain sciences*, 2(4), 637-638. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0140525X00064955>
- Bramlett, M., & Blumberg, S. (2017). Family structure and children's physical andmental health. *Health Affairs*, 26(2), 549-558. <https://doi.org/10.1377/hlthaff.26.2.549>
- Chanda, K., & Pujar, A. (2018). Stress and psychological well- being among single parents. *International Journal of Pure and Applied Bioscience*, 6(4), 226-232. <http://dx.doi.org/10.18782/2320-7051.6692>
- Chansaengsee, S. (2018). Time management for work-life and study-life balance. *Veridian E-Journal, Silpakorn University (Humanities, Social Sciences and Arts)*, 10(5), 20-34.
- Chen, S., Richardson, S., Kong, Y., Ma, N., Zhao, A., Song, Y. & Li, Z. (2023). Association between parental education and simultaneous malnutrition among parents and children in 45 low-and middle-income countries. *JAMA Network Open*, 6(1), e2251727-e2251727. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamanetworkopen.2022.51727>
- Clarke, V., & Braun, V. (2017). Thematic analysis. *The Journal of Positive*, 12(3),297-298. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17439760.2016.1262613>
- Clark, H., Coll-Seck, A. Banerjee, A., Peterson, S., Dalglish, S. Ameratunga, & Costello, A. (2020). A future for the world's

- children? A who–UNICEF- lancet commission. The Lancet, 395(10224),605-658. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(19\)32540-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(19)32540-1)
- Corbett, M. & Forsey, M. (2017). Rural youth out-migration and education: Challenges to aspirations discourse in mobile modernity. *Discourse: Studies in the Cultural Politics of Education*, 38(3), 429-444. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01596306.2017.1308456>
- Creswell, J., Cuevas, S., Karen, G. & Robinson, L. (2019). *Qualitative inquiry and research design: Choosing among five approaches*, 2007. Tehran: Saffar. [in Persian].
- Cumyn, A., Ouellet, K., Côté, A., Francoeur, C. & St-Onge, C. (2019). Role of researchers in the ethical conduct of research: A discourse analysis from different stakeholder perspectives. *Ethics & Behavior*, 29(8), 621-636. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10508422.2018.1539671>
- Czeisler, M., Lane, R., Petrosky, E., Wiley, Christensen, A., Njai, R., & Rajaratnam, S. M. (2020). Mental health, substance use, and suicidal ideation during the COVID-19 pandemic—United States, June 24–30, 2020. *Morbidity and Mortality Weekly Report*, 69(32), 1049. <https://dx.doi.org/10.15585/mmwr.mm6932a1>
- Dangal, M. & Joshi, R. (2020). Hermeneutic phenomenology: Essence in educational research. *Open Journal for Studies in Philosophy*, 4(1). <https://doi.org/10.32591/coas.ojsp.0401.03025d>
- Devine & Hughes, C. (2018). Family correlates of false belief understanding in early childhood: A meta-analysis. *Child Development*, 89(3), 971-987. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cdev.12682>
- Dibley, L., Dickerson, S., Duffy, M. & Vandermause, R. (2020). *Doing hermeneutic phenomenological research: A Practical Guide*. Sage. <https://doi.org/10.4135/978152979958>
- Doepke, M., Sorrenti, G., & Zilibotti, F. (2019). The economics of parenting. *Annual Review of Economics*, 11, 55-84. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-economics-080218-030156>
- Elijah, J. (2017). Challenges every indian single parent faces. <https://www.youthkiawaaz.com/2017/10/single-indian-parents-things-we-need-to-understand/>
- Epstein, J. (2018). School, family, and community partnerships in teachers' professional work. *Journal of Education for Teaching*, 44(3), 397-406. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02607476.2018.1465669>
- Gading, L. (2019). The roles of single parent. *European Journal of Special Education Research*. <https://dx.doi.org/10.46827/ejse.v0i0.2594>
- Garriga & Berta, P. (2018). Single-mother families, mother's educational level, children's school outcomes. *Unequal Family Lives*, 143. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781108235525.007>
- Gentles, S., Charles, C., Ploeg, J. & McKibbin, K. (2017). Sampling in qualitative research: Insights from an overview of the methods literature. *The Qualitative Report*, 20(11), 1772–1789. <https://doi.org/10.46743/2160-3715/2015.2373>
- Gingerbread. (2018). Paying the price: The impact of the summer budget on single parent families. https://gingerbread.org.uk/file_download.aspx?id=9519Gingerbread.
- Gupta, A., & Kashyap, S. (2020). Growing up in a single parent family; A determining factor of adolescent's well-being. *Advanced Journal of Social Science*, 7(1), 138-144. <https://doi.org/10.21467/ajss.7.1.138-144>
- Heng, E. (2017). Plight of single families. <https://www.theborneopost.com/2017/02/26/plight-of-single-parent-families/>
- Hennink, M., Hutter, I. & Bailey, A. (2020). *Qualitative research methods*. Sage. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11135-023-01660-5>
- Hickey, G., & Kipping, C. (1998). Exploring the concept of user involvement in mental health through a participation continuum. *Journal of Clinical Nursing*, 7(1), 83-88. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0020764016675376>
- Holden, G. (2019). *Parenting: A dynamic perspective*. Sage publications. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781452204000>
- Hopwood, C. (2018). Interpersonal dynamics in personality and personality disorders. *European Journal of Personality*, 32(5), 499-524. <https://doi.org/10.1002/per.2155>
- Hotz, V. McElroy, S., & Sanders, S. (2018). The impacts of teenage childbearing on the mothers and the consequences of those impacts for government. In *Kids having kids* (pp. 55-94). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780429452635-3>
- Ifcher, J., & Zarghamee, H., (2018). The happiness of single mothers: Evidence from the general social survey. *Journal of*

Happiness Studies, 1(5), 1219– 1238. doi:10.2139/ssrn.1740029.

Javier, J., Aliganga, F., Supan, J., & Palinkas, L. (2018). Voices of the Filipino community describing the importance of family in understanding adolescent behavioral health needs. *Family & Community Health*, 41(1), 64. DOI: 10.1097/FCH.0000000000000173

Johnson, A., Chafouleas, S., & Briesch, A. (2017). Dependability of data derived from time sampling methods with multiple observation targets. *School Psychology Quarterly*, 32(1), 22. <https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1037/spq0000159>

Kafle, N. (2018). Hermeneutic phenomenological research method simplified. *Bodhi: An Interdisciplinary Journal*, 5(1), 181-200. <https://doi.org/10.3126/bodhi.v5i1.8053>

Kalil A, Ryan R, Corey M. Diverging destinies: Maternal education and the developmental gradient in time with children. *Demography*. 2018; 49:1361– 1383. [PubMed: 22886758] <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13524-012-0129-5>

Karos, K., Williams, A., Meulders, A., & Vlaeyen, J. (2018). Pain as a threat to the social self: a motivational account. *Pain*, 159(9), 1690-1695. DOI: 10.1097/j.pain.0000000000001257. https://journals.lww.com/pain/citation/2018/09000/pain_as_a_threat_to_the_social_self__a.6.aspx

Khosla, I. (2021). Optimism and psychological well-being in Indian adults: Exploring gender and age differences. *Indian Journal of Positive Psychology*, 12(2). <https://openurl.ebsco.com/EPDB%3Aagcd3A9%3A16763945/detailv2?sid=ebsco%3Aplink%3Ascholar&id=ebsco%3Aagcd%3A151691436&crl=c>

Kim, J., Lee, J., & Lee, S. (2018). Single mothers' experiences with pregnancy and child rearing in Korea: Discrepancy between social services/policies and single mothers' needs. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 15(5), 955. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph15050955>

Kiral, B. (2019). The rights and responsibilities of parents according to the views of teachers. *Asian Journal of Education and Training*, 5(1), 121-133. <https://doi.org/10.20448/journal.522.2019.51.121.133>

Koketso, M., Calvin, M., Lehlokwe, S., & Mafa, P. (2019). Perspectives of single mothers on the socio-emotional and economic influence of absent fathers in child's life: A case study of rural community in south Africa. *e-BANGI*, 16, 1-12. <https://ejournal.ukm.my/ebangi/issue/view/1185>

Kotwal, N., & Prabhakar B. (2019). Problems faced by single mothers. *Journal of Social Sciences*, 21(3), 197-204. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09718923.2009.11892771>

Kuppens, S., & Ceulemans, E. (2019). Parenting styles: A closer look at a well-known concept. *Journal of Child and Family Studies*, 28, 168-181. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10826-018-1242-x>

Kuscuoglu, A., & Hartas, D. (2022). Academic self-concept, self-esteem, and school attitudes in pre and mid adolescents: Gender, SES and parenting. *Research Papers in Education*, 1-24. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02671522.2022.2150885>

Kutash, K., Duchnowski, A., Green, A., & Ferron, J. (2018). Supporting parents who have youth with emotional disturbances through a parent-to-parent support program: A proof of concept study using random assignment. *Administration and Policy in Mental Health and Mental Health Services Research*, 38, 412-422. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10488-010-0329-5>

Kruglanski, A., Bélanger, J., Gelfand, M., Gunaratna, R., Hettiarachchi, M., Reinares, F., & Sharvit, K. (2018). Terrorism-A (self) love story: Redirecting the significance quest can end violence. *American Psychologist*, 68(7), 559. <https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1037/a0032615>

Kyngäs, H., Kääriäinen, M., & Elo, S. (2020). The trustworthiness of content analysis. *The application of content analysis in nursing science research*, 41-48. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-30199-6_

Law, E., Fisher, E., Eccleston, C., & Palermo, T. (2019). Psychological interventions for parents of children and adolescents with chronic illness. *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews*, (3). <https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD009660.pub4>

Lindsay, T., & Gillum, N. (2018). Exploring single-mother college students' perceptions of their college-related experiences and of campus services. *The Journal of Continuing Higher Education*, 66(3), 188-199. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07377363.2018.1537657>

Listiana, A. (2021, March). The Single parent's parenting style. In 5th international conference on early childhood education (ICECE 2020) (pp. 140-143). Atlantis Press. <https://doi.org/10.2991/assehr.k.210322.030>

Mabuza, SK Thwala, CIO Okeke (2017) Single parenting and its effects on the psychosocial development of children in Swaziland. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 5(23). <https://doi.org/10.5901/mjss.2014.v5n23p2252>

- Madigan, S., Prime, H., Graham, S., Rodrigues, M., Anderson, N., Khoury, J., & Jenkins, J. (2019). Parenting behavior and child language: A meta-analysis. *Pediatrics*, 144(4). <https://doi.org/10.1542/peds.2018-3556>
- Malachi, R. (2020). Positive and negative effects of single parenting. http://www.momjunction.com/articles/effect-of-single-parenting_00373930/
- Maldonado, L., & Nieuwenhuis, R. (2019). Single parents in context. *Future Child*, 5, 75-96. DOI: 10.1093/OBO/9780199756384-0220
- Marcil, L., Hole, M., Jackson, J., Markowitz, M., Rosen, L., Sude, L., & Vinci, R. (2021). Anti-poverty medicine through medical-financial partnerships: A new approach to child poverty. *Academic Pediatrics*, 21(8), S169-S176. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.acap.2021.03.01>
- Marett, E., Marler, L., & Marett, K. (2018). Socioemotional wealth importance within family firm internal communication. *Journal of Family Business Management*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JFBM-08-2017-0022>
- Martínez, I., Murgui, S., Garcia, O., & Garcia, F. (2019). Parenting in the digital era: Protective and risk parenting styles for traditional bullying and cyberbullying victimization. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 90, 84-92. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2018.08.036>
- Marzocchi, S. (2020). Faith and politics in Otto III's Monumenta. *Historica. Frühmittelalterliche Studien*, 54(1), 233-256. <https://doi.org/10.1515/fmst-2020-008>
- Maxwell, J. (2021). Why qualitative methods are necessary for generalization. *Qualitative Psychology*, 8(1) <https://psycnet.apa.org/record/2020-36022-001>. <https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1037/qap0000173>
- McLanahan, S., & Beck, A. N. (2018). Parental relationships in fragile families. *The Future of children/Center for the Future of Children, the David and Lucile Packard Foundation*, 20(2), 17. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2307/20773693>
- McLoyd, V. (2021). The impact of economic hardship on black families and children: Psychological distress, parenting, and socioemotional development. *Child Development*, 61(2), 311-346. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8624.1990.tb02781>
- Meevissen, Y., Peters, M., & Alberts, H. (2018). Become more optimistic by imagining a best possible self: Effects of a two-week intervention. *Journal of Behavior Therapy and Experimental Psychiatry*, 42(3), 371-378. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbtep.2011.02.012>
- Meier, A., Musick, K., Fischer, J., & Flood, S. (2018). Mothers' and fathers' well-being in parenting across the arch of child development. *Journal of Marriage and Family*, 80(4), 992-1004. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jomf.12491>
- Mikolajczak, M., Gross, J., & Roskam, I. (2019). Parental burnout: What is it, and why does it matter. *Clinical Psychological Science*, 7(6), 1319-1329. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2167702619858430>
- Mokake, N. (2021). Single motherhood and its consequences on children; A case comparison of Sweden and Germany. https://www.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:1557035/full_text_01.pdf
- Montes, C. (2021). Legal ethics implications accepting and handling marriage nullity cases under the family code of the philippines: The intersection between Aristotelian Thomistic ethics and the code of professional responsibility. *U. Asia & Pacific LJ*, 3, 1. <https://heinonline.org/HOL/LandingPage?handle=hein.journals/uaplj3&div=5&id=&page=>
- Mooney, A., Oliver, C., & Smith, M. (2019). Impact of family breakdown on children's well-being. Evidence reviews. *Journal of Sociology and Social Work*. 5. 149-158. <http://dx.doi.org/10.15640/jssw.v5n1a15>
- Moreno-Ruiz, D., Martínez-Ferrer, B., & García-Bacete, F. (2019). Parenting styles, cyberaggression, and cybervictimization among adolescents. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 93, 252-259. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2018.12.031>
- Moser, A., & Korstjens, I. (2018). Series: Practical guidance to qualitative research. Part 3: Sampling, data collection and analysis. *European Journal of General Practice*, 24(1), 9-18. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13814788.2017.1375091>
- Mudau, T., Mukansi, L., & Ncube, D. (2018). The effects of single parenting on raising teenagers: A case study of the Hasani Dakari village Vhembe district in Limpopo province, South Africa. *Gender and Behaviour*, 16(2), 11728-11739. <https://hdl.handle.net/10520/EJC-131f356a00>
- Mugove, K. (2017). Challenges encountered by single parents in the learning and development of children, *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, 7(6), 178-186. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/challenges+encountered+-+by+single+parents+-+in+-+the+-+and+-+development+of+children.KudengaMugove/ade152485508ca857aebb636c5c063ae7f040546>
- Nam, Y., & Hanna, S. (2019). The effects of risk aversion on life insurance ownership of single-parent households. *Applied Economics Letters*, 26(15), 1285-1288. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13504851.2018.1546044>

- Napora, E., Andruszkiewicz, A., & Basińska, M. (2017). Types of work-related behavior and experiences and stress coping strategies among single mothers and mothers in relationships differentiating role of work satisfaction. *International Journal of Occupational Medicine and Environmental Health*, 31(1), 55-69. <https://doi.org/10.13075/ijomeh.1896.01052>
- Nelson, M. (2019). *Parenting out of control: Anxious parents in uncertain times*. New York University Press; 2019. <https://doi.org/10.18574/nyu/9780814759080.001.0001>
- Nigar, N. (2020). Hermeneutic phenomenological narrative enquiry: A qualitative study design. *Theory and Practice in Language Studies*, 10(1), 10-18. <http://dx.doi.org/10.17507/tpsls.1001.02>
- Nishioka, D., Saito, J., Ueno, K., & Kondo, N. (2021). Single-parenthood and health conditions among children receiving public assistance in Japan: A cohort study. *BMC Pediatrics*, 21, 1-9. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12887-021-02682-4>
- Nurgaliyeva, A., Childibayev, D., Sagyndykova, S., Azman, M., & Saparova, G. (2022). Scientific and methodological basis of practice-oriented training of students-biologists: A case study in Kazakhstan. <https://journal.unnes.ac.id/nju/jpii/article/view/33057>
- Oerther, S. (2020). Analysis methods in hermeneutic phenomenological research: Interpretive profiles. *Frontiers of Nursing*, 7(4), 293-298. <https://doi.org/10.2478/fon-2020-0038>
- Offer, S. (2019). Time with children and employed parents' emotional well-being. *Social Science Research*, 47, 192-203. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssresearch.2014.05.003>
- Odumosu, J. (1997). Divorce, socio-economic status, and children's cognitive-social competence at school entry. *American Journal of Orthopsychiatry*, 54 (3): 459-468. <https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1111/j.1939-0025.1984.tb01511.x>
- Oluwayemisi, J., Enema, A., Hamdalla, A., Aira, O., Umma, B., Habiba, I., & Sunday, S. (2018). A cross-sectional study of traditional practices affecting maternal and newborn health in rural Nigeria. *Pan African Medical Journal*, 31(1). <https://doi.org/10.11604/pamj.2018.31.64.15880>
- O'Neill, O. (2018). Linking trust to trustworthiness. *International Journal of Philosophical Studies*, 26(2), 293-300. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09672559.2018.1454637>
- Pollmann-Schult, M. (2019). Single motherhood and life satisfaction in comparative perspective: Do institutional and cultural contexts explain the life satisfaction penalty for single mothers. *Journal of Family Issues*, 39(7), 2061-2084. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0192513X17741178>
- Powell, B. (2019). Changing counts, counting change: Toward a more inclusive sciences, 17(1), 1-15. <https://digitalcommons.butler.edu/jiass/vol17/iss1/2%0AThis>
- Prihartono, M., & Asandimitra, N. (2018). Analysis factors influencing financial management behavior. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 8(8), 308-326. <http://dx.doi.org/10.6007/IJARBSS/v8-i8/4471>
- Qutoshi, S. (2018). Phenomenology: A philosophy and method of inquiry. *Journal of Education and Educational Development*, 5(1), 215-222. <https://doi.org/10.22555/joeed.v5i1.2154>
- Rahul, H. (2018). Regulation of pharmacy council of India and assessment of quality life among single mother-by-choice 'residing in slums linkage pharmaceutical institutions in pune, India. *Drug Des Int Prop Int J* 1 (3)-2018. DDIPIJ. MS. ID, 115(1), 2. <https://doi.org/10.32474/ddi.pij.2018.01.000115>
- Raja, D., (2020). Advantages and disadvantages of single parenting. https://www.momjunction.com/articles/advantages-and-disadvantages-of-single-parenting_00372990/.
- Raymo, J. (2017). The well-being of single mothers in Japan. In *life course, happiness and well-being in Japan* (pp. 116-137). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315266114-7>
- Richard, J., & Lee, H. (2019). A qualitative study of racial minority single mothers' work experiences. *Journal of Counseling Psychology*, 66(2), 143. <https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1037/cou0000315>
- Richter, D., & Lemola, S., (2017). Growing up with a single mother and life satisfaction in adulthood: A test of mediating and moderating factors. *PLoS One*, 12(6), 1-15. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0179639>.
- Sanders, M., & Turner, K. (2018). The importance of parenting in influencing the lives of children. *Handbook of parenting and child development across the lifespan*, 3-26. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-94598-9_1
- Sicam, E., Umawid, M., Colot, J., Dagdag, J., & Handrianto, C. (2021). Phenomenology of parenting while schooling among filipino college student mothers in the province. *Kolokium*, 9(2), 80-94. <https://doi.org/10.24036/kolokium-pls.v9i2.483>

- Silverman, D. (Ed.). (2020). *Qualitative research*. sage. <https://doi.org/10.7748/nr.19.2.45.s3>
- Skubiejūtė, G. (2019). Children in single mother families: Outcomes of social construction and policy design of single mother families. *People: International Journal of Social Sciences*, 5(2), 643-661. <https://doi.org/10.20319/pijss.2019.52.643661>
- Stack, R., & Meredith, A., (2018). The impact of financial hardship on single parents: An exploration of the journey from social distress to seeking help. *J Fam Econ Iss*, 39, 233–242. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10834-017-9551-6>.
- Stanca L. (2017) Suffer the little children: Measuring the effect of parenthood on well-being worldwide. *Journal of Economic Behavior and Organization*. 2017; 81:742–750. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jebo.2010.12.019>
- Standing, M. (2017). A new critical framework for applying hermeneutic phenomenology. *Nurse Researcher*, 16(4). doi: 10.7748/nr2009.07.16.4.20c7158. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/19653543/>
- Stephen, E., & Udisi, L., (2018). Single-parent families and their impact on children: A study of amassoma community in bayelsa state. *European Journal of Research in Social Sciences*, 2(9), 1-24. <https://www.idpublications.org/wp-content/uploads/2016/10/Full-Paper-single-parent-families-and-their-impact-on-the-children-a-study-of-amassoma-community.pdf>
- Sundler, A., Lindberg, E., Nilsson, C., & Palmér, L. (2019). Qualitative thematic analysis based on descriptive phenomenology. *Nursing Open*, 6(3), 733- 739. <https://doi.org/10.1002/nop2.275>
- Tang, W., Wang, G., Hu, T., Dai, Q., Xu, J., Yang, Y., & Xu, J. (2018). Mental health and psychosocial problems among Chinese left-behind children: A cross-sectional comparative study. *Journal of Affective Disorders*, 241, 133- 141. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jad.2018.08.017>
- Taylor, Z., & Conger, R. (2017). Promoting strengths and resilience in single- mother families. *Child Development*, 88(2), 350-358. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cdev.12741>
- Trochim, Prof. William M. (2020, March 10). *Qualitative approaches*. <https://conjointly.com>
- Van Gasse, D., & Mortelmans, D. (2020). With or without you—starting single- parent families: A qualitative study on how single parents by choice- reorganise their lives to facilitate single parenthood from a life course perspective. *Journal of Family Issues*, 41(11), 2223-2248. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0192513X20911971>
- Vela, J., Sparrow, G., Whittenberg, J., & Rodriguez, B. (2018). The role of character strengths and importance of family on Mexican American college students' career decision self-efficacy. *Journal of Employment Counseling*, 55(1), 16-26. <https://doi.org/10.1002/joec.12070>
- Veronika, M., & Afdal, A. (2019). Differences in self-concept of students from intact families and non-intact families. *Jurnal Aplikasi IPTEK Indonesia*, 3(3), 151-58. <https://doi.org/10.24036/4.33282>
- Villalobos, A. (2019). Compensatory connection: Mothers' own stakes in an intensive mother-child relationship. *Journal of Family Issues*, 36(14), 1928-956. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0192513X13520157>
- Viswambharan, A., & Priya, K. (2018). Documentary analysis as a qualitative methodology to explore disaster mental health: Insights from analyzing a documentary on communal riots. *Qualitative Research*, 16(1) 43–59. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1468794114567494>
- Vlaeyen, J., & Crombez, G. (2020). Behavioral conceptualization and treatment of chronic pain. *Annual review of clinical psychology*, 16(1), 187-212. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-clinpsy-050718-095744>
- Walther, J., Sochacka, N., Benson, L., Bumbaco, A., Kellam, N., Pawley, L., & Phillips, C. (2017). Qualitative research quality: A collaborative inquiry across multiple methodological perspectives. *Journal of Engineering Education*, 106(3), 398-430. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jee.20170>
- Wajim, J., & Grace, S., (2020). Single parenting and its effects on the development of children in Nigeria. *The International Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities Invention* 7(03): 5891-5902. <https://doi.org/10.18535/ijsshi/v7i04>.
- Warburton, W., Whittaker, E., & Papić, M. (2018). Homelessness pathways for Australian single mothers and their children: An exploratory study. *Societies*, 8(1), 16. <https://doi.org/10.3390/soc8010016>
- Watt, P. (2018). Gendering the right to housing in the city: Homeless female lone parents in post-olympics, austerity East London. *Cities*, 76, 43-51. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cities.2017.04.005>
- Weinraub, M., & Kaufman, R. (2019). Single parenthood. In *handbook of parenting* (pp. 271-310). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780429433214-8>
- Wellman, H. M., & Gelman, S. A. (1992). Cognitive development: Foundational theories of core domains. *Annual review of*

psychology, 43(1), 337-375. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.ps.43.020192.002005>

Whisenhunt, J., Chang, C., Parrish, M., & Carter, J. (2019). Addressing single parents' needs in professional counseling: A qualitative examination of single parenthood. *The Family Journal*, 27(2), 188-198. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1066480719835343>

Wood, E., Kennison, S., & Jackson, G. (2019). The role of parenting style of single parents in young children risk-taking. *Current Psychology*, 1-10. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12144-019-00178-0>

Wray, D. (2022). How do work-family policies shape parents' time with children? (Doctoral dissertation, University of Toronto (Canada). <https://www.proquest.com/openview/8629f5bc6a58a05dc0dbd81974e16930/1?pq-origsite=gscholar&cbl=18750&diss=y>

Zhang, L., & Liu, Z. (2018, March). Ethical issues in research processes: Informed consent, the role of the researcher, access to research sites and research subjects. In 2nd international conference on culture, education and economic development of modern society (ICCESE 2018) (pp. 505-508). Atlantis Press. <https://doi.org/10.2991/iccese-18.2018.117>

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